

GreenDIGIT

Greener Future Digital Research Infrastructures

Deliverable D5.1: Reproducible platform design with a web-based Virtual Research Environment

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Executive Summary

The GreenDIGIT project's Deliverable 5.1 presents a web-based Virtual Research Environment (VRE) that streamlines scientific research by making it more sustainable, reproducible, and aligned with Open Science principles. Built on the widely used Jupyter notebook platform, the VRE guides researchers through the entire experiment lifecycle, from planning and execution to analysis and sharing. By connecting with federated data management infrastructures (FDMI), it ensures research outputs are easily discoverable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable, adhering to FAIR data standards. This integration fosters collaboration and transparency across scientific communities.

At the core of the VRE is a 4-Pillar Conceptual Reproducibility Framework, which provides a structured approach to defining experiments clearly, executing them consistently, and preserving them for future use. This framework minimises redundant experiments, saving resources and enhancing trust in results. The VRE extends Jupyter with tools to support sustainable research, including a design extension that creates portable experiment workflows. Additionally, this 4-pillar reproducibility framework is prototyped with a use case system called EcoJupyter, a plugin that offers real-time tracking of energy consumption and carbon footprint through intuitive metrics like Software Carbon Intensity, empowering researchers to make environmentally conscious decisions. Moreover, the automated workflow is implemented to push experiment data on FDMI to enhance the reproducibility. The SLICES Metadata Registry Service (MRS) is used to organise experiment data into a searchable, structured format that complements the RO-Crate standard, ensuring long-term accessibility and preservation. Automated publishing to federated platforms simplifies sharing, making research outputs widely available and reusable.

The VRE's flexible, modular design supports a range of scientific domains and is built to evolve. Improvements include enhanced user interfaces and stronger integration with repositories such as Zenodo and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). By embedding sustainability and reproducibility, the GreenDIGIT VRE reduces resource waste and promotes transparent, impactful science, setting a strong foundation for responsible research aligned with global sustainability goals.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ACM	Association for Computing Machinery
API	Application Programming Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DUT	Device under Test
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FDO	FAIR Digital Object
FDMI	Federated Data Management e-Infrastructure
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High-Performance Computing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MUI	Material UI
MRS	Metadata Registry Service
NTP	Network Time Protocol
PID	Persistent Identifier
pos	plain orchestrating system
PRaaS	Platform Research Infrastructure as a Service
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAPL	Running Average Power Limit
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDE	Research Development Environment
RDM	Research Data Management
RESTful API	Representational State Transfer API
RI	Research Infrastructure
RO-Crate	Research Object Crate
SCI	Software Carbon Intensity
SFDO	SLICES FAIR Digital Object
SUT	System under Test
VM	Virtual Machine
VRE	Virtual Research Environment
VRI	Virtual Research Infrastructures
W3C PROV	The World Wide Web Consortium Provenance Model
WP	Work Package
WPS	Web Processing Service
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1 Introduction

Data-driven analyses have become integral to research across many scientific domains, not just computer science. Therefore, researchers from many different domains use specific or general-purpose digital Research Infrastructures (RIs) as part of their scientific workflow. The GreenDIGIT project aims to improve the environmental sustainability of RIs with a holistic approach covering many aspects of experimental workflows. A vital part of the project activities in Work Package (WP) 5 is the creation of an RI platform for researchers, which accompanies and supports them throughout the whole experiment lifecycle from the initial idea up to the publication and potential re-execution by different researchers. A special focus of this platform is to provide researchers with suitable support for creating reproducible scientific results. As a consequence, well-documented, metadata-enriched, and Open-Science and FAIR-compliant research artifacts can be automatically published, for example, in federated data management e-infrastructures (FDMIs). To realise such workflows, GreenDIGIT WP5 developed a Virtual Research Environment (VRE). Scientific experiments typically cause significant environmental impact [1]. With its structured research approach, it analyses environmental impact and contributes to lowering this impact. Resource-intensive re-creation and evaluation of datasets can be avoided in many cases due to well-documented, findable, and portable results. The research platform is a basis for research tools, which, in the context of GreenDIGIT, are developed in Deliverable D5.2. Due to the heterogeneity of existing RIs, Jupyter notebooks have been identified as a suitable and widely-used foundation for the VRE, for which extensions aimed at reproducibility and environmental impact assessment have been developed.

1.1 Contributions

This document introduces a comprehensive framework designed to enhance the reproducibility of scientific experiments, encompassing their entire lifecycle. We present a definition of the conceptual reproducibility framework that underpins our approach, integrating Research Object Crate (RO-Crate)¹ extensions to facilitate reproducible workflows and the capture of all metadata, required for findability, reproducibility, and environmental impact assessment. Our solution offers a platform for reproducible experiments within a web-based VRE, aiming to provide trustworthy results and thus avoid experiment repetition. This is realised in a Minimum Viable Prototype (MVP) deployed in the GreenDIGIT/SoBigData web-based VRE, providing an end-to-end workflow for packaging, validating, and publishing Experiments. Upon publication, the workflow supports deposition to Zenodo and the generation of a DOI. A key focus is on assisting in experiment design for Open Science practices, while also contributing to the reduction of environmental impact by optimizing resource utilization. Furthermore, we detail the tooling to publish and store research artifacts, ensuring that research results are publishable in a federated data management infrastructure and readily accessible for verification and reuse.

¹<https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>

1.2 Structure of the Document

The rest of the document is structured as follows:

Chapter 2 introduces key approaches and background concepts relevant to scientific research in general and to this deliverable in particular, such as FAIR, Open Science, or reproducibility. Chapter 3 introduces key design aspects of the reproducible platform to realise research according to the GreenDIGIT goals. In Chapter 4, we describe the architecture of the developed extensions for the VRE to support additional services for experimental workflows. Next, in Chapter 5, the implementation aspects are explained. In Chapter 6, further developments and an outlook on coming WPs are provided. Chapter 7 concludes this deliverable.

2 Background

2.1 FAIR and Open Science

Open Science, Research Data Management (RDM), and Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) principles are important aspects in modern RIs design and operation. They also define the important functionalities and the required services of VREs capable of facilitating and implementing the reproducibility of research.

2.1.1 Open Science, Research Data Management, and FAIR Principles in the Context of RIs and VREs

The integration of Open Science practices and FAIR data principles into the operation of RIs and VRE is central to ensuring the transparency, reusability, and societal impact of scientific research. These frameworks collectively define a new paradigm for responsible and sustainable research practice, where data and results are accessible, traceable, and reusable by design.

Open Science advocates for the unrestricted sharing of scientific outputs, including publications, data, methods, and tools, with the wider research community. In the context of RIs and VREs, this means that all research assets produced or processed within digital environments should be openly available under clear licensing terms, ideally through trusted repositories and community-maintained platforms. The Open Science ecosystem includes open access publishing, open data sharing, open-source software, and open workflows, which together enhance the transparency and reproducibility of research processes.

RDM is a foundational component of Open Science. Effective RDM ensures that data generated throughout the research lifecycle, from data collection to scientific output preservation, are well-structured, documented, and stored securely. Within digital infrastructures, RDM must be embedded into the design and operation of services that support project teams, institutional data stewards, and domain scientists. Key RDM practices include the definition of metadata standards, use of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), implementation of access control mechanisms, and adherence to legal and ethical requirements such as data privacy and intellectual property rights.

Central to modern RDM is the adoption of the FAIR guiding principles that include Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability of research data. These principles enable both humans and machines to effectively discover, access, and reuse research data across infrastructures and disciplines. FAIR compliance is realised through machine-actionable metadata, semantic interoperability frameworks, and infrastructure services such as PIDs, metadata registries, and trusted repositories. The FAIR Digital Object (FDO) model, supported by initiatives such as the FDO Forum and Research Data Alliance (RDA) [2], operationalises FAIR by binding data and metadata into uniquely identified, reusable entities that integrate with infrastructure-level services.

For RIs and VREs, implementing these principles requires developing a set of technical and policy-based solutions, in particular:

- Metadata management systems that support community standards and vocabularies.
- FAIR-compliant repositories for publishing and archiving research outputs.
- PID services for support references, discovery and access for datasets, software, workflows.
- Policy enforcement frameworks that ensure compliance with access rights, licenses, and data protection regulations (these should be implemented in the RI operation).

It is important to admit that Open Science and FAIR practices should be supported by introducing the data stewardship roles embedded in infrastructure governance to provide guidance and oversight throughout the data lifecycle.

Tools and interfaces within VREs must support researchers in producing, documenting, and publishing FAIR and open research outputs without requiring excessive technical knowledge. This includes integrating DMP templates, reproducibility checklists, and metadata annotation tools directly into the research workflows and experiment management systems.

By aligning RDM practices with Open Science and FAIR principles, RIs and VREs will not only ensure scientific rigour and reproducibility but also enhance data sustainability, knowledge dissemination, and long-term societal value of publicly funded research.

2.1.2 Virtual Research Environment for Reproducibility and Sustainability

In the evolving landscape of digital RIs, ensuring that experimental research is reproducible, transparent, and sustainable is both a scientific necessity and a policy imperative. The concept of VRE emerges from the proposed in earlier authors' publications the Platform Research Infrastructure as a Service (PRIaaS) model [3]. PRIaaS defines a high-level, conceptual and architectural framework for future RIs that are policy-aware, modular, and compliant with European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) architecture recommendations [4]. It provides the essential theoretical basis upon which more concrete and layered GreenDIGIT Architecture Framework (refer to the project Deliverable D4.2 [5]). has been developed, and in particular, the Pillar 1 Layered and Modular Architecture for Sustainable Digital Infrastructures.

PRIaaS introduces a modular and layered approach to infrastructure, in which research services are structured across distinct yet interoperable components, ranging from physical and virtualised infrastructures to domain-specific tools, workflows, and user-facing interfaces. This modularity enables the flexible deployment of tailored environments, referred to as Virtual Research Infrastructures (VRIs), that can be dynamically instantiated to meet the needs of specific scientific communities or experimental contexts.

Building on the general concepts introduced in PRIaaS, the GreenDIGIT architecture elaborates a layered and modular structure for sustainable digital RIs. In this context, the VRE spans the upper three layers (upper Layers 3, 4, and 5) of the GreenDIGIT architecture, each of which functionally embodies and extends key PRIaaS principles into operational components.

At Layer 3, infrastructure is virtualised and provisioned dynamically through the Actualisation Platform—a concept rooted in PRIaaS. This layer supports the creation of tailored VRIs that abstract

the complexity of heterogeneous physical resources and embed orchestration mechanisms such as DevOps and DataOps to support scalable experimentation and integration.

Layer 4 defines the Research Development Environment (RDE), which provides containerised tools, scientific workflow engines, and domain-specific Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). These components are designed to ensure reproducibility through automated provenance capture, reuse of workflows, and traceable execution pipelines. The RDE reflects the goal of infrastructure-agnostic tooling and policy-driven research enablement.

Layer 5, the user interaction and collaboration layer, hosts researcher portals, dashboards, notebooks, and community interfaces. It embodies Open Science values by enabling transparency, openness, and trust in the research process. This layer supports federated authentication, collaboration spaces, and open dissemination of both data and results.

Across all three layers, the VRE operationalises the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) [6]. Experiments, datasets, workflows, and software are treated as FDOs [7] with PIDs, standardised metadata, and semantic annotations. These elements are organised using packaging formats such as RO-Crate and stored in EOSC-compatible repositories, ensuring machine-actionability, discoverability, and long-term reusability.

Sustainability is targeted to be deeply embedded in the VRE design, not only from an environmental perspective but also in terms of governance, automation, and lifecycle management. Data and workflows are associated with enforceable policies, covering access, licensing, provenance, and ethical compliance, which persist as data moves across federated infrastructures. This enables responsible and legally compliant reuse, supporting the long-term sustainability of research outputs and infrastructures.

GreenDIGIT Architecture Framework presents a vision for the next generation of VREs: research environments that are FAIR-by-design, aligned with Open Science, and capable of supporting reproducible, policy-compliant, and sustainable experimental research across diverse digital ecosystems.

2.2 Reproducibility in the Context of Computational Experiments

For computer science, the Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) [8] considers three different stages for reproducibility:

- **Repeatability** is achieved if the same people use the same setup to repeat results;
- **Reproducibility** is achieved if different people use the same setup to reproduce results;
- The final stage, named **Replicability**, is reached if different people use different setups to replicate results.

In 2015, Collberg and Proebsting [9] studied the replicability of computer science publications. They concluded that the lack of replicability is considered sociological, not technological, as little reward can be gained from replication. They propose to solve the issue in the long term through a cultural

change toward the appreciation of replication. However, as a short-term solution, they suggested that the funding agencies should provide funds dedicated to making publications repeatable.

2.3 Reproducibility as Key to Sustainability

Meyn et. al. argue that irreproducible research has various negative consequences [1]. Scientific experiments are typically resource-intensive (material and intellectual resources), causing significant environmental impact. Several approaches, such as reproducible and transparent research and sharing of best practices, methodologies, and resources, can help limit this impact.

More recent developments have suggested that in computer science, reproducibility and replicability are gaining considerable attention. In 2003, the first ACM SIGCOMM workshop took place, addressing reproducibility [10]. In 2017, a second workshop on replicable network experiments was held at the ACM SIGCOMM conference [11]. In 2019, a Dagstuhl seminar on this topic was held, in which guidelines for replicable network experiments have been established [12]. These guidelines consider the entire lifecycle of an experiment: from the experiment description to its execution, evaluation, and finally to the publication of artifacts. The push toward reproducibility and replicability is not limited to ACM SIGCOMM, as other scientific communities are currently establishing a culture of experiment replication and Artifact Evaluation Committees [13]. Saucez et al. [14] evaluated the Artifact Evaluation Committees of CoNEXT'18 and other SIGCOMM-sponsored conferences and journals. A survey conducted on the interviewed authors and reviewers considered the experience gained to be useful and interesting. However, the artifact evaluation can be time-consuming for reviewers. Although considerable attention is paid to reproducibility, achieving it takes time and effort. Zilberman [15] conducted a case study, demonstrating that even papers awarded with ACM's reusable badge may not show a complete picture of the investigated system behaviour. She found that low robustness, i.e., small variation from the original input, such as the investigated packet size, could lead to a significantly different output.

In 2024, a **Dagstuhl Seminar [16]** was held on the topic of "RIs and Tools for Collaborative Networked Systems Research". The workshop was organised by Georg Carle and Serge Fdida, long-term contributors to SLICES-RI and further partners of GreenDIGIT. One of the goals of this workshop was to bring together the testbed community, researchers from the community of computer networks that use the testbeds, and the data management community. Recommendations from this workshop include an implementation of FAIR data principles into testbed-driven research by using well defined standardised metadata describing the experimental research data and a publication on relevant repositories such as Zenodo or OpenAIRE. Reproducibility and its support by the testbed are also decisive factors to bring forward the research community. Sustainability is highly relevant for this community. On the one side, RIs must be used in a responsible way to minimise the environmental impact of operating the platform. On the other side, the research performed on these platforms should be selected with sustainability in mind.

The Dagstuhl recommendations also include other recommendations important for the GreenDIGIT project in alliance with SLICES-RI development: (i) common/standard information model for experiment description (supported by FAIR metadata definition) that can integrate existing

networking/infrastructure configuration data and experiment description data: (ii) introducing metrics and incentives in experiment governance that would include testbed measurable operational Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) which may include sustainability metrics; (iii) “malleable experiment workflows” and testbed independent workflow definition that can facilitate experimental research reproducibility and further Open Science and FAIR compliance.

3 Architecture of the Web Platform for Experimental Research Reproducibility

In this chapter, the architecture of the GreenDIGIT VRE is described based on the background information covered in the previous chapter.

3.1 Layered VRE Architecture and Components

In the previous parts, requirements have been defined, and the Jupyter ecosystem has been identified as a very widespread basis of VREs supported by many RIs. Hence, we base the GreenDIGIT VRE on the Jupyter ecosystem. To create a platform for reproducible and sustainable experiments, we extend the Jupyter ecosystem with plugins and additional integrations to make specific functionality available for researchers and researcher tools (c.f. D5.2).

Figure 1 depicts the VRE within the Architecture Framework for digital RI for Sustainability by Design, which is introduced in the GreenDIGIT Deliverable D4.2. The layered VRE architecture complies with the first pillar mandates a layered and modular architecture for RIs.

Layer 1: The lowest layer, Layer 1, consists of data centre and physical infrastructure resources, which, depending on the particular RI, are not accessible to the researcher. The GreenDIGIT VRE accesses power distribution units and energy meters from Layer 1. Also, it provides interfaces to Prometheus monitoring feeds. If available, Scaphandre is another useful Layer 1 resource.

Layer 2: For reproducibility purposes, the VRE platform includes access to storage resources and requires interfacing with resource reservation and allocation functionality, which are provided by Layer 2, representing cloud and virtualised infrastructure resources.

Layer 3: Layer 3 unites different VRI building blocks for RI virtualisation and provisioning. The VRE accesses resource Initialisation and available task and workflow execution primitives.

Layer 4: The GreenDIGIT VRE is positioned on Layer 4. It consists of three extensions based on Jupyter Notebook. For one, there is an impact assessment dashboard, for another, a reproducible experiment design extension, and for still another, the FDMI integration agent and API. These blocks access resources from lower layers.

Layer 5: Researcher tools on Layer 5 are able to access VRE and according extensions.

The following sections describe the architecture elements of the GreenDIGIT VRE in more detail.

Figure 1: VRE within the layered and modular architecture for sustainable digital infrastructure

3.2 4-Pillar Framework for Conceptual Reproducibility and Requirements to Virtual Research Environment

Reproducibility is foundational to scientific research, yet achieving reproducibility remains challenging in experimental information and communications technology (ICT) research due to the diversity of tools, testbeds, and practices. This section presents the "4-Pillar Framework for Conceptual Reproducibility," a structured and modular approach tailored to digital RIs. The framework supports both **reproducibility** (different team, same setup) and **portability** (testing the same hypothesis across different setups), making it particularly suited for RIs with intended extension to support environmental sustainability aspects in experiment management, documenting and reproducibility. This is defined as a conceptual reproducibility providing a basis for reproducibility of complex multifactor/cross-domain research that can evolve in complexity and abstraction.

Experimental research in ICT domains often involves complex, distributed, and rapidly evolving systems. These characteristics introduce significant challenges for ensuring the reproducibility of results. Traditional approaches to reproducibility do not fully accommodate the heterogeneity and federation of modern RIs. The 4-Pillar Framework offers a conceptual and operational foundation to address this gap by structuring reproducibility across four key dimensions that reflect the actual workflow of ICT experimental researchers.

3.2.1 Key Properties

The following **key properties** characterise the *4-Pillar Framework for Conceptual Reproducibility*:

- **Non-linear adoption:** Researchers can integrate existing or legacy work into 4-pillar framework.

- **Modularity:** Interoperability between the different pillars is ensured by consistent common information of the experiment or scientific research.
- **Reusability-first:** Focuses on packaging experiment intent, execution, and outputs for future adaptation.
- **Alignment with open science:** Designed to be EOSC-compatible and FAIR-aligned, using standardised formats such as RO-Crate.

3.2.2 The 4-Pillar Conceptual Reproducibility Framework

The four pillars are defined as follows:

Pillar 1: Conceptual Experiment Definition and Formalised Description

This pillar focuses on defining the scientific intent of the experiment. It encompasses the articulation of hypotheses, identification of variables, and specification of the conceptual model. By separating the scientific logic from implementation details, this pillar enhances the portability of results across diverse environments. Pillar 1 supports the conceptual clarity and portability across different implementations.

Key components:

- Hypothesis and objective formulation
- Identification of dependent and independent variables
- Definition of experiment types (e.g., benchmarking, validation)
- Use of structured formats and documentation tools
- Optional semantic annotation using domain-specific ontologies

Pillar 2: Experiment Design and Deployment

This pillar addresses the formal, machine-readable description of experiments and their mapping to infrastructure. It facilitates deployment across testbeds through declarative specifications and infrastructure abstraction.

Key components:

- Declarative experiment specifications (e.g., YAML, OEDL, CWL)
- Resource modelling and network topology definition
- Provisioning and orchestration APIs
- Support for federated and heterogeneous environments

Pillar 3: Workflow Execution, Measurement, and Monitoring

Ensuring accurate and synchronised execution is essential for reproducibility. This pillar includes the use of automated workflows, standardised measurement tools, and proper calibration. It supports robust data collection and contextualisation.

Key components:

- Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery integration for experiment automation
- Time synchronisation protocols (Network/ Precision Time Protocol (NTP/PTP))

- Metric collection and validation (e.g., latency, throughput)
- Use of standard formats (JSON-LD, CSV)
- Annotation of execution conditions and environment

Pillar 4: Research Lifecycle Support, Preservation, and Publication

This pillar integrates reproducibility into the full research lifecycle, from experiment execution to dissemination. It aligns with FAIR principles and promotes the long-term preservation and sharing of research artifacts.

Key components:

- RO-Crate packaging for structured data outputs
- PIDs (DOIs, Handles)
- Provenance tracking using standards (e.g., The World Wide Web Consortium Provenance Model (W3C PROV))
- Integration with EOSC, Zenodo, OpenAIRE
- Support for publishing negative results and deviations

Based on the described pillars, the following requirements can be identified to ensure the reproducibility of experiments using the VRE:

- Support users to define and structure their experiments
- Offer facilities for resource modelling
- Orchestration of heterogeneous environments through APIs
- Provision of services supporting the preparation of the experimental environment such as resource allocation or time synchronisation
- Automated execution of experiment workflows and collection of experiment results using well-known formats
- Provision of services supporting the preservation and publication of experimental results, such as standardised archives (RO-Crate), tagging using PIDs (DOIs), or the publication in open repositories (e.g., Zenodo)

The requirements listed above reflect fundamental properties required across different scientific domains. The different scientific domains may have specific additional requirements such as the RIs in GreenDIGIT that target different domains. SLICES, for instance, aims to create an RI for the ICT domain. Therefore, SLICES requires specific features to describe and record network topologies or highly distributed research environments, whereas RIs that focus on high-performance computing, such as EGI, focus on the provision of high-performance resources, e.g., GPUs.

The following sections of this deliverable describe how the requirements are reflected in the GreenDIGIT VRE.

3.2.3 Extending 4 Pillars Framework for Energy Efficiency and Environmental Sustainability

The 4 Pillars Conceptual Reproducibility Framework allows adding specific types of information in the experimental research description/documentation to support energy and environmental impact aware reproducibility. In relation to pillars, the following information and measurements should be added and provided.

Pillar 1: Conceptual Experiment Definition and Formalised Description

Suggested additions for energy/environment focus: Environmental objectives, energy as a variable, experiment type (e.g., energy profiling, thermal benchmarking).

- Clearly state environmental and energy-related hypotheses or objectives
- Define energy consumption or carbon footprint as dependent or observed variables if relevant.

Pillar 2: Experiment Design and Deployment

Suggested additions: Energy-aware infrastructure specs, resource/energy models

- Extend experiment model with defining
 - Hardware energy profiles (Central/Graphics Processing Unit (CPU/GPU) power specs, energy-efficient hardware features).
 - Energy constraints as part of resource and experiment environment requirements.
- Include infrastructure-specific energy capabilities (e.g., energy meters, green energy source usage).
- Describe whether virtualisation, containerization, or bare-metal setups are used, and how they impact energy use.

Pillar 3: Workflow Execution, Measurement, and Monitoring

Additional ICT/compute/network-specific measurements to include: Energy and carbon metrics, measurement tools, execution conditions

1. Energy consumption metrics:

- Total energy used (kWh or Joules).
- Real-time power draw (watts).
- Energy per transaction or per packet (for network experiments).

2. Environmental metrics:

- Carbon emissions (CO₂e), if using carbon calculators tied to regional energy sources.
- Ambient and device temperature (affects energy efficiency and reproducibility).

3. Instrumentation details (type, configuration, precision):

- Type and precision of energy monitoring tools (e.g., Running Average Power Limit (RAPL), Intelligent Platform Management Interface, Power Distribution Units, external meters).
- Measurement interval and synchronisation method.

4. Execution environment annotations:

- Hardware/firmware version.
- Operating conditions (e.g., cooling state, data centre Power Usage Efficiency (PUE) if available).
- Power management settings (e.g., CPU frequency scaling).

Pillar 4: Research Lifecycle Support, Preservation, and Publication

Suggested additions: Energy-aware RO-Crates, provenance of energy conditions, sustainability metadata, compliance, in particular:

- Include energy and environmental metadata in RO-Crate packages or equivalent research artifacts, if applicable, use provenance records (e.g., W3C PROV).
- Publish negative results or deviations linked to energy-performance trade-offs.
- Where possible, associate datasets with:
 - Energy context (green/renewable energy use, carbon offset declarations).
 - Sustainability tags (e.g., “green computing”, “low-power mode”).
 - Define compliance with the policy, regulations, and/or standards defined methodology, metrics and KPIs.

3.2.4 Reproducing Experiment with Energy/Environmental Impact Aware Documentation

To repeat or reproduce an ICT/networking experiment while accounting for energy consumption and environmental impact, the process must go beyond functional correctness and performance validation. It should ensure that energy-related behaviour and execution conditions are meaningfully compared across runs and setups. The following is a suggested sequence for Energy/Environment-Aware Reproducibility, extending the traditional reproducibility steps with sustainability-aware controls and measurements.

Step 1: Define the energy-relevant Hypothesis and Objectives

Analyse the experiment description, e.g. documented as RO-Crate, to clarify what aspect was documented and expected to be evaluated:

- **Energy efficiency** (e.g., lower energy use under same workload).
- **Carbon footprint** (e.g., impact of region/power source).
- **Thermal performance or cooling influence.**

Implementation condition: Ensure the experiment includes energy or emissions as necessary dependent variables.

Step 2: Match execution environment (or describe differences explicitly)

Ensure repeating on the same or comparable hardware, or assess possible deviation:

- Same CPU/GPU model, memory size, storage type.
- If different, describe energy/performance differences explicitly.

- Ensure energy monitoring infrastructure is present and calibrated.

Implementation condition: Document differences using structured metadata: hardware specs, power modes, virtualization layers.

Step 3: Align environmental conditions

Record and match the environmental condition of the reproducibility setup:

- Ambient temperature.
- Cooling methods.
- Time of day or load on shared infrastructure.

Consider **data centre PUE** or **green energy share** if available.

Implementation condition: Reproduction should be limited to comparable thermal and energy provisioning environments.

Step 4: Calibrate measurement tools

Calibration is an important aspect of a reproducibility environment. It is achieved by verifying

- Power sensors are enabled (e.g., RAPL, external wattmeter).
- Sampling frequency and accuracy are consistent.
- Time synchronization across monitoring tools (NTP/PTP).

Implementation condition: Energy metrics are only comparable if collected with the same resolution, timing, and tool chain.

Step 5: Repeat experiment workflows (at least 3–5 iterations/runs)

By controlled experiment execution, for each run, collect:

- Execution logs (task times, phases).
- Energy measurements (Joules/kWh).
- Carbon emissions estimates (grams CO₂e).

Implementation condition: Multiple runs help capture variability due to thermal drift or load-dependent energy usage.

Step 6: Compare Against Baseline or Original Results

Ensure comparability of the reproducible experiment execution. Include normalising results:

- Energy per task/transaction.
- Emissions per unit of output (e.g., per trained model or per Mb transferred).

Check for reproducibility within confidence bounds (e.g., $\pm 5\%$) should be included in the reproducibility workflow and validation.

Implementation condition: Energy-aware reproducibility may tolerate slight performance differences but requires trend consistency.

Step 7: Report deviations and environmental factors

Required reporting:

- Unexpected differences in energy draw or CO₂ output.

- Infrastructure behaviour (e.g., CPU frequency throttling).
- Any non-determinism due to system load or cooling behaviour.

Implementation condition: Documenting deviations is essential for trustworthy sustainability evaluations.

Step 8: Package and share the results

Common and recommended use:

- RO-Crate with energy and emissions metadata.
- W3C PROV to show provenance of energy data.
- Public repositories (e.g., Zenodo) to share reproducibility results and context.

The following is an illustration of the energy/environment-aware reproducibility loop/workflow

4 Design of the Web Platform for Experimental Reproducibility

4.1 Jupyter Notebook/Ecosystem as Basis of the Virtual Research Environment

4.1.1 Background on Jupyter

The predecessor of Jupyter² is IPython, which was originally developed as an enhanced interactive shell for the Python programming language. IPython provided a powerful environment for interactive computing, allowing users to execute code in a live session, inspect results immediately, and manipulate data dynamically. This interactivity made it especially suitable for scientific computing and data analysis workflows.

The transition from IPython to Jupyter began when the IPython project introduced a notebook interface, which combined executable code, rich text, equations, visualisations, and other media into a single, shareable document known as a *notebook*. This innovation allowed users to structure and document their computational narratives in a more coherent and reproducible manner. The resulting tool quickly gained popularity across scientific disciplines.

As the project matured, the notebook interface was decoupled from IPython and generalised to support other programming languages besides Python. This evolution led to the creation of Project Jupyter, with support for multiple languages such as Julia, R, and others through a modular kernel architecture.

Today, Jupyter ecosystem includes three components/platforms:

- Jupyter Notebook³ - a web-based interface to create and run interactive documents called notebooks (supporting code, text, math, plots, etc.);
- JupyterLab⁴ - the next-generation interface for Project Jupyter, offering a more flexible and extensible environment (like an IDE including file browser, terminals, consoles, and supporting plugins);
- JupyterHub⁵ - a multi-user server for Jupyter Notebooks and JupyterLab, enabling projects and organisations (e.g., universities, research labs) to host Jupyter environments for multiple users.

Jupyter Notebook platform and tools are widely adopted in both academia and industry as a versatile platform for data science, machine learning, scientific research, and education. It supports collaborative work, reproducibility of experiments, and integration with cloud-based services and

²<https://jupyter.org/>

³ Jupyter Notebook - <https://github.com/jupyter/notebook>

⁴ JupyterLab <https://discourse.jupyter.org/c/jupyterlab/17>

⁵ JupyterHub - <https://jupyterhub.readthedocs.io/en/latest/explanation/concepts.html>

version control systems. Jupyter Notebooks have become a cornerstone in the data science ecosystem, enabling users to combine code, documentation, and visualisations in a single, interactive computing environment.

4.1.2 Jupyter Notebook for Testbeds

Jupyter is also used as interface for other purposes than pure data processing. A notable platform that uses Jupyter is the US-based Chameleon testbed [17]. On the Chameleon platform, the entire experiment workflow is embedded into a Jupyter notebook, that defines the experiment. The notebook contains the setup of the experiment, the actual measurement performed during the experiment, and the final evaluation of data. All of these steps are collected in a single notebook simplifying a later reproduction. The Chameleon testbed also maintains a repository where experiments can be published that is called Trovi⁶. However, there is neither a standard nor a recommendation how these notebooks should be structured. This results in a unique design for each notebook, unnecessarily complicating the process of understanding or reusing existing notebooks for one's own research. The plain orchestrating system (pos) offers a way to structure experiments that simplifies their understanding and potential reuse. This structure can be represented as a Jupyter notebook⁷. In Section 4.3 we describe the concept how experiments can be mapped to Jupyter notebooks.

4.1.3 Jupyter Notebooks/ecosystem for RIs

All participating RIs (SoBigData, EBRAINS, EGI, SLICES-RI) use Jupyter Notebooks as part of their research development environment, in particular, using EGI Notebook, the JupyterHub based hosting platform⁸. Therefore, the Jupyter Notebook was identified and chosen as a common platform to allow an execution of notebooks on the different platforms.

4.2 Reproducibility by Design

Reproducibility is achieved through a set of properties of the research project. The VRE aims to guide researchers in designing reproducible research artifacts. This process needs to accompany the whole experimental lifecycle. Data models and metadata are needed for a structured and interoperable approach, and experimental records need to be stored in an accessible and reproducible format.

4.2.1 Experimental Lifecycle

The Experimental Lifecycle is typically divided into four phases:

- Phase 1: The initial phase identifies specific research questions or problems, creates hypotheses and defines a scope for the experiment
- Phase 2: This phase focuses on the design of the experiment. In this phase, a prototype is created to test the validity of the hypotheses.

⁶<https://trovi.chameleoncloud.org/dashboard/artifacts>, last accessed: 2025-05-20

⁷<https://github.com/gallenmu/pos-jupyter>, last accessed: 2025-05-20

⁸ <https://docs.egi.eu/users/dev-env/notebooks/>

- Phase 3: The execution of the experiment to collect the experiment data. The data collection is typically monitored to ensure the quality of the experiment. If necessary, adjustments are made to correct or improve the data generation and collection.
- Phase 4: Analysis and evaluation of the collected data. This can involve the statistical evaluation or plotting of data. These results are then used for reports, publications, or presentations.

Phase 1 is a creative scientific process that requires specific domain knowledge and cannot be provided through a standardised process. The creative process and the required domain knowledge come from the specific scientific fields and communities. All participating RIs target a subgroup of scientific fields, such as the neuro-science community (EBRAINS), research on social networks (SoBigData), high-performance computing with multiple different user domains (EGI), or the information technology domain (SLICES-RI). The RIs support their respective communities, offering examples that a community can use as input to set up new experiments. SLICES has realised this process in the form of blueprints. These blueprints are community-driven experimental platforms that can be reused by research groups for their experiments. An example of such a blueprint is the SLICES Post 5G Blueprint that creates a working 5G network environment to allow research for the ICT (Information & Communication Technology) domain. Researchers can reuse this platform provided by SLICES-RI to realise their own experiments including modifications to the existing code or completely new applications based on 5G networks. Thereby, researchers can focus on their domain knowledge and avoid spending time on creating a platform for their experiments.

The participating RIs in GreenDIGIT operate infrastructures. Therefore, RIs traditionally have a strong focus on **Phases 2 and 3** of the experiment lifecycle, that involves the creation of experiments and their execution. This part of the experiment lifecycle is typically realised using Jupyter notebooks. These notebooks support different scripting languages that can be used to create prototypes for testing hypothesis. The live-modification of code through the Jupyter interface allows fast iteration cycles to refine experiments. The actual experiment can be controlled and executed through Jupyter notebooks either based on the previous prototype or entirely new experiment notebooks. As mentioned in previous sections, all participating RIs offer and encourage users to use Jupyter notebooks. The notebooks are executed on the various backends offered by the respective RIs that take care of executing the experiments. A key feature of scientific experiments is their reproducibility. An example of how RIs, such as SLICES-RI, can support users to implement this feature as part of their experiment cycle is explained in previous sections.

In GreenDIGIT, we want to highlight and provide researchers with support for **Phase 4**. Many experimental platforms, such as Chameleon or CloudLab do not support this phase of the experiment workflow. Users can still use the platform to evaluate experiments. However, without platform support, researchers implement their own solutions. This creation process leads to redundant developments, lowering the scientific output and future reuse. We detail our contributions in the following sections, with a focus on structuring experimental results and the publication process. Platforms supporting such a structured process can help avoid redundant development and help users reuse existing experimental data described through a rich set of metadata.

4.2.2 Metadata to Describe Experiment and Supporting Infrastructure

Metadata are an important component of experiments, documenting and supporting DMI that provides a basis for services interoperability, experimental research reproducibility, effective data sharing and discovery. Effective and consistent metadata management is the foundation of the FAIR data principles implementation. All data are defined by the data models, metadata, data formats and data types. Metadata are defined as part of the data model.

RIs have to deal with metadata in regard to different stages of scientific experiments. For SLICES-RIs experimental studies in digital technologies and ICT, metadata includes three main areas:

- General services description: metadata profiles and metadata will be used for publishing SLICES services in EOSC Catalogue and the SLICES services catalogue;
- Description of data collected, produced and handled in SLICES-RI that include experimental data, staged/processed data, archival data, publications, reports, and management data. Additional data categorisation is required;
- Experiment description that includes all necessary information for experiment reproducibility and deployment.

Two other categories of metadata may be required to support SLICES experiments:

- Infrastructure descriptions that are required for infrastructure management and monitoring (network devices, network traffic, status and events). This type of metadata is well supported by existing network and service management standards (SNMP MIB-II, DMTF CIM and CIMI);
- Metadata for data processing and lineage, in particular, for data used in Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence processes.

Defining domain-specific metadata requires the definition of the metadata schema and namespaces that create a basis for unique metadata elements identification and consequently discovery, sharing and integration.

4.2.2.1 Experiment Data Model and Required Metadata

To provide a full experiment description and achieve the experiment reproducibility all experiment setup, control and execution must be supported by the consistent experiment model and documented at the time of execution and during the whole research lifecycle [18] [19]. All documented data must be FAIR compliant: Findable and Accessible after publishing to ensure research sharing, and further Interoperable and Reusable to achieve full reproducibility.

Figure 2 illustrates the generic experiment data model including the following components:

- Device/System under Test (DUT/SUT) model (variables, parameters, environment)
- DUT/SUT Configuration & Setup
- Test/Stimulus Variables& Parameters, possibly also including environment parameters
- Measurement (instruments) configuration

Figure 2: Generic experiment data model for reproducibility.

For consistent and reliable experiment description and documenting, the properly defined metadata must be defined and applied for all experiment components and stages. Additional aspect in supporting experimental data collection is the proper data model selection and corresponding database support. The relational data model and corresponding database platform are considered as the most relevant taking into account that the experiment description and setup will use multiple tables (for setup and test generation).

The following sections describe data used and collected from two components of SLICES-RI: pos and the Post 5G Blueprint, which are in the process of integration for running the experiments. This integrates the experiment management but from the data management point of view it will require smooth data integration addressing common and interoperable metadata definition and correspondingly defining the consistent experiment data model.

4.2.2.2 pos experiment description and metadata

Consistent/full experiment description and corresponding metadata must ensure experiment/experimental research reproducibility and FAIR data sharing.

The following data types and metadata are considered essential for consistent experiment description (based on pos implementation and suggestions):

- Experiment abstract model with parameters, input variables and variables under test (as it is known at the beginning).
- Experiment setup/infrastructure, including network equipment and the network topology, including Virtual Machines (VMs)/containers
 - Hardware: list of major hardware components (e.g., CPU, network cards, memory, storage).

- Firmware: version numbers of the installed firmware, e.g., Basic Input/Output System version, CPU microcode version, firmware version of the network card.
- Software: version of the investigated software and its installed dependencies, version of the installed OS (including version of OS kernel), software installed on the OS.
- Configuration of all infrastructure components, deployment sequence (such as Ansible playbook, Terraform plan, or Jupyter Notebook).
- Test generators, measurement equipment and sensors (and corresponding infrastructure points)
 - Specification of the generated traffic (the content of the traffic).
 - Specification of the patterns used for the generated traffic (e.g., a distribution of the inter-packet gaps or traffic bursts).
- Environment description (hardware/software).
- Experiment workflow (the usage of pos ensures reproducibility of experiment workflow).
- Data ingest process, data preprocessing and assessment.
- APIs for experiment setup, monitoring, and data collection .

Data models and metadata must be defined for all types of data describing the experiment.

For some well-established experiments, data models may be defined for the specific data storage and database type, such as data lakes, Structured Query Language database, key-value, document based, or triple storage (for semantic data).

As a part of the experimental research environment, experiment can be considered as a Research Object (RO), documentation and management of which is supported by the research community practices and frameworks [20]. Experiment as a RO must be assigned a unique identifier and experiment/object type, optionally registered schema and domain namespace.

Goal of reproducibility: The goal of reproducible experiments is the reproduction of key performance descriptors for a specific experiment. The exact reproduction of these key performance descriptors may depend on specific hardware and software that may change over time. We rather aim for recording a complete picture of the environment an experiment is conducted in. The recorded information is the foundation to find differences between experiment executions that may not be obvious during the initial experiment.

The usage of POS ensures the collection of many aspects mentioned before. To generate the necessary information for the experiment description, pos relies on standard Linux tools. Typical tools to automate the hardware description would be `lshw` that lists all hardware (and some of the firmware versions). Additional, more specialised tools may be used for other hardware components, such as `ethtool` for network cards. The testbed itself may provide information about the topology, that should be detected regularly (e.g., using tools for topology detection such as `lldp`).

We propose to record the typical format provided by the mentioned tools. A testbed should provide an abstraction layer to access the mentioned information in a more generalised format to simplify further processing. Testbed tools such as pos already provide a common data format (JSON) to unify the output of the different tools.

4.2.2.3 *SLICES Post 5G Blueprint Architecture for 5G/6G and related networking technologies*

SLICES Blueprint defines a basic/core/instant infrastructure setup that can be used for running experiments on 5G/6G and related networking technologies. The Post 5G Blueprint is defined in a modular way that allows defining basic building blocks or design patterns that can be composed in a different way to create a platform for running different experiments.

To achieve effective composability and flexible customisation of the SLICES experimental setups, the following data and metadata should be defined (similar for the general experiment setup as described above):

- Services deployed in the Post 5G Blueprint and corresponding APIs.
- Input and output data or signals.
- Configuration of all elements, including Radio Access Network (RAN) (RU – Radio Units, UE – User Equipment), core 5G network, dedicated network (VPN or VPC), network switches, servers.
- Computational nodes/instances type and configuration: hardware (AMD/Intel, RAM, OS, firmware)
- Operational environment that may need to be documented for experiments.
- Infrastructure design patterns or templates (in the form of Ansible playbooks or Terraform plans).
- Monitoring or measurement point and corresponding API.
- Experiment-specific or other data collected in the infrastructure.

4.3 Documenting Experimental Research with RO-Crate

A key objective of the GreenDIGIT VRE is to ensure that experimental outputs are not only technically reproducible but also portable, transparent, and aligned with principles of sustainability and Open Science. To achieve this, the VRE integrates support for structured postprocessing, long-term preservation, and automated publication of research results. At the core of this approach is the adoption of RO-Crate, a standardised and extensible format for packaging experimental outputs with rich metadata.

RO-Crate, as introduced by Soiland-Reyes et al. [21], is a specification for describing and encapsulating Research Objects using a JSON-LD⁹ (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data) structure. It provides a human- and machine-readable format for expressing relationships between data files, software, creators, and other contextual elements. RO-Crate makes it possible to define the origin, structure, and meaning of a dataset or workflow in a consistent and interoperable manner.

⁹ <https://json-ld.org>

Figure 3: RO-Crate concept of packaged results and metadata

Figure 3 gives an overview of this basic concept. On the left side, it shows metadata elements such as author details (e.g., ORCID) and organisational identifiers (e.g., ROR), while on the right side, result and configuration files are illustrated. Together, these components are bundled into a self-contained RO-Crate package. This encapsulation forms the foundation for both attribution and reuse. It also serves as a universal format for experiment preservation and publication.

In the context of GreenDIGIT, the RO-Crate format is a useful basis for experiments and their results to capture the full lifecycle of an experiment, including its environmental impact. Figure 4 demonstrates the structure of an RO-Crate. Each experiment conducted via the VRE produces a structured result folder that contains configuration information (e.g., hardware setup, used variables, installed software), scripts (setup, measurement, evaluation), and result files (histograms, plots, energy data). These components are centrally described and linked through a *ro-crate-metadata.json* file located at the root of the folder. This metadata file establishes semantic links between the components and captures creator information, file formats, and the logical relationships among experiment elements. Also, part of an RO-Crate may be the measured the energy data of this workflow. RO-Crate is used not only to document scientific outcomes, but also to track power consumption profiles, statistical evaluations, and voltage patterns that emerge during the experiment. These data are linked to the responsible software, hardware, and experimental parameters, enabling reproducible energy analysis across infrastructures and over time.

Figure 4: Folder Structure of an RO-Crate

Figure 5 illustrates this applied structure. The visual representation shows how the main folders - */config*, */scripts*, and */files* - contain all components of the experiment, including energy-specific outputs. These are all referenced and described in the central metadata file. Once the experiment is complete, the full RO-Crate can be published to external repositories such as Zenodo¹⁰ or integrated RIs like SoBigData¹¹. These platforms support PIDs and FAIR data indexing, which enables citation, tracking, and reuse.

¹⁰ <https://zenodo.org/>

¹¹ <https://sobigdata.d4science.org/>

Figure 5: RO-Crate lifecycle

Integration with SoBigData.eu enables GreenDIGIT outputs to reach a wide research audience. SoBigData serves as both a hosting platform and a community interface, allowing published experiments to be incorporated into workflows, reused in new contexts, and evaluated with additional tools. By enabling automated publication into this infrastructure, GreenDIGIT aligns reproducibility and sustainability with broader scientific discoverability. The usage of the RO-Crate format enables a seamless transition from local experimentation to accessible, documented, and

reproducible research artifacts. This supports not only technical reproducibility, but also long-term preservation, verifiability, and community engagement across different RIs. The practical benefits of RO-Crate for structuring experimental artifacts have been demonstrated in testbed-driven environments through the MARTE framework [22]. MARTE extends the RO-Crate concept to enable reproducibility and long-term preservation of experiments by integrating both metadata and execution logic into a self-contained artifact. It supports two complementary approaches: record-replay, which automatically captures all issued instructions during an experiment, and malleable reproduction, which retains editable scripts and configuration files for flexible re-execution. In this context, RO-Crate not only provides semantic structure but also serves as the foundation for automated provenance tracking, artifact publication, and cross-infrastructure portability. MARTE showcases how such a setup allows experimenters to reproduce results with minimal effort and share them via persistent repositories like Zenodo or integrated infrastructures such as SoBigData.

4.3.1 RO-Crate and Metadata Registry Service (MRS): Complementary Solutions for Data Structuring

RO-Crate offers a standardised approach for structuring archives of experimental results, bringing clear benefits such as compliance with the FAIR data principles, which simplify data reuse. However, RO-Crate was not originally designed as an online format intended for active exploration or modification. Its flexible architecture allows it to accommodate a wide variety of archived artifacts, but this flexibility also introduces a limitation: much of the metadata describing an RO-Crate is optional.

By contrast, metadata formats tailored to specific types of data or experimental workflows may sacrifice some flexibility in favour of enforcing mandatory fields that capture critical domain-specific information. This trade-off can enhance the value of such metadata formats for researchers working within particular scientific disciplines.

Importantly, RO-Crate's flexible design permits full custom, RO or experiment specific metadata definition, which is defined by a `ro-crate-metadata.json` file, part of the RO-Crate archive. The research environment (represented by VRE) should support the RO/RO-Crate metadata profile creation and linking with the experiment description.

The metadata management service and tools are developed as a part of the Common Information Model, defined in the GreenDIGIT Architecture Framework Pillar 4 and described in detail in Deliverable 5.2. To ensure interoperability with the SLICES experimental and testbed platforms, the GreenDIGIT metadata management will re-use and be compatible with the SLICES **Metadata Registry Service (MRS)**, developed as part of **SLICES-RI** and used in the **Post 5G Blueprint**. The metadata format and a service to manage the metadata was developed as part of SLICES-DS¹² and SLICES-PP¹³ projects, the latest pre-production version of this service is described in a recent publication [23]. The MRS uses open, standardised formats like JSON and is supported by a service

¹² <https://www.slices-ds.eu/>

¹³ <https://www.slices-pp.eu/>

that enables live search, filtering, and management of metadata. While at first glance, RO-Crate and the MRS appear to address similar needs—structuring data—they actually serve orthogonal purposes. RO-Crate defines a static archival format, whereas the MRS facilitates dynamic interaction with metadata.

In contrast to RO-Crate’s loose metadata requirements, the SLICES-MRS imposes a more rigid schema with mandatory fields, offering a more structured and searchable dataset. Despite these differences, the two approaches can be integrated: MRS metadata can be encapsulated within an RO-Crate archive without violating RO-Crate compliance.

This integration becomes particularly relevant in scenarios where the MRS service is discontinued, such as when SLICES-RI reaches the end of its operational lifespan. In such cases, archiving MRS metadata in RO-Crate format ensures long-term preservation and accessibility.

The SLICES-RI MRS was also picked up by other flagship projects, such as 6G-Sunrise, as a solution to structure their metadata. The MRS and its metadata model have the following features:

Flexible hierarchical metadata model: The metadata model includes a domain-agnostic and a domain-specific part to describe digital artifacts with mandatory metadata attributes and more specific additional attributes. If needed, the model can be extended with new attributes, types/categories, or hierarchy levels. SLICES-RI uses a flexible, hierarchical model with three levels. The first level captures compulsory, domain-agnostic metadata (e.g., identification, description, resource type, version) for any digital object, ensuring alignment with FAIR and open science standards. The second level contains compulsory, type-specific metadata enhances machine-actionability for common digital object types (e.g., datasets with start/end dates, services with addresses). The third level includes optional, domain-specific metadata improves interoperability within specialised communities.

Hybrid Metadata Production (Human + Machine): SLICES streamlines metadata creation with automated tools (e.g., for dates, attributes) and supports manual input (e.g., descriptions, keywords) for user-defined metadata. The automation and the validation of the input ensure the availability of metadata and their quality.

Wide-ranging Interoperability: Metadata supports semantic (object discovery), legal (usage restrictions), and technical (system communication) interoperability. SLICES-RI ensures compatibility with external systems (e.g., EOSC, aggregators) by enabling transformation to standard formats (e.g., DublinCore, OpenAIRE).

Long-term Reusability: The evolving SLICES metadata model includes versioning for both the model and its vocabularies, ensuring clarity over time. Users and systems can access version details via dedicated services. SLICES-RI supports metadata crosswalks with key standards (e.g., RDA, EOSC, Dublin Core, Datacite 4.3, DCAT 2.0).

Enhanced Discovery: SLICES-RI enables both simple and advanced (query-based) discovery using manual and automated descriptors, including metadata extraction (e.g., date, size) and built-in data analysis (e.g., basic statistics).

Metadata Quality Assurance: A framework within the Data Governance Group will use defined metrics to assess metadata quality, FAIRness, and other key objectives.

Open-Source: SLICES-RI has launched a working group to foster community engagement and improve metadata and data management through open-source contributions.

MRS implements the SLICES metadata model, offering access and management for compliant digital objects. Its architecture includes three components: a Postgres database for metadata storage, a backend exposing a REST API with authentication and compatibility features, and a web portal for user interaction. The web portal can be integrated with the experiment management platform such as POS. In particular, it is fully integrated into the SLICES Post 5G Blueprint which is used for running specific types of experiments on the Post 5G testbed operated by the SLICES-RI [24].

The MRS provides a REST API to access and manage the metadata describing the publishable experiment outcome as a SLICES FAIR Digital Object (SFDO) [25], which is compatible with the EOSC Resource metadata profile [7] [26]. This interface can be used to provide accessibility either for a human-readable UI or for machine-to-machine interfaces to further process the data. The MRS is also integrated with the authentication method (OpenID Connect) of the SLICES blueprints, to provide secure, authenticated (meta)data access.

4.4 Impact Assessment Dashboard Design

The Impact Assessment Dashboard is a Jupyter Lab plugin showing statistics of environmental impact. It uses metrics provided by Prometheus and Scaphandre. Those are industry standard monitoring and energy metering solutions. In the layered architecture, the integration happens in the following manner:

Layer 1 (Data centre and Infrastructure Resources): deploying agents like Scaphandre at the node level, collecting metrics directly related with the RAPL interface enabling aggregation by Prometheus.

Layer 2 (Cloud and Virtualised Infrastructure): the tool prototype and use-case is built with a Kubernetes-based JupyterHub (Helm) for orchestration and management—mimicking containerised virtualised research environments within federated RIs. Metrics are gathered per user (Spawner) in an isolated manner.

Layer 3 (Platform for RI Virtualisation and Provisioning): EcoJupyter interacts with resource provisioning layers through configuration managements such as Helm Charts and ConfigMaps; enabling integration into different cluster setups.

Layer 4 (Research Development Environment and Scientific Workflow): within EcoJupyter managed Jupyter Notebooks, researchers execute structured workflows and experiments. The dashboard complements this by enabling runtime feedback and post-execution reporting using raw metrics, KPIs and other metadata.

Layer 5 (Researcher Tools and Portal): the dashboard is directly accessible and installable in JupyterLab’s interface as a plugin. It is a portable tool which offers refreshable plots, exportable data, and API communication with external services (e.g., FDMI from SoBigData).

4.4.1 Architecture and Technology Stack

To emulate realistic usage conditions in high-performance computing environments, EcoJupyter was deployed in a *Kubernetes-based JupyterHub* setup. This orchestration approach ensures scalability, reproducibility, and efficient resource allocation—principles that apply the operational models of many modern RIs.

The technology stack includes:

- **Kubernetes** for orchestration and resource isolation.
- **Helm-based JupyterHub** for managed multi-user Jupyter environments.
- **Scaphandre** as the energy monitoring agent deployed per user pod.
- **Prometheus** for scraping, storing, and querying time-series metrics exposed by agents.

This architecture enables experiment-specific metric collection while preserving a modular structure for scaling and adaptation.

4.4.2 Pod Instrumentation: Sidecar vs In-Pod Integration

Two architectural strategies were evaluated:

- **Sidecar approach:** Easy to adopt, automatically spawns a monitoring agent alongside each user notebook pod. However, it lacks opt-in control, introduces infrastructure management overhead, and hinders portability.
- **In-pod (user-controlled) deployment:** Chosen as the final approach, this method empowers users to initialise metric collection themselves using the Jupyter extension. It supports opt-in/opt-out control, is lightweight, and better aligns with platform-agnostic deployment goals.

The latter was chosen for providing more flexibility and less overhead from the infrastructure management point of view.

Configuration and Repository

The deployment is reproducible via public Helm and YAML configuration files hosted at a publicly available Github repository EcoJupyter¹⁴.

Key files include:

- `config-jhub-local.yaml` – local deployment configuration for JupyterHub
- `ConfigMaps` for default notebook initialisation and user environment setup

Extension Pipeline and Backend Integration

¹⁴ <https://github.com/g-uva/EcoJupyter>

EcoJupyter's frontend is a JupyterLab extension built with TypeScript and published via PyPi, allowing automated distribution and updates (see Figure 6 for the pipeline). The frontend connects to the backend through Jupyter's `IKernelConnection` interface, issuing `executeRequest()` calls to run pre-defined code snippets in the user's active notebook session.

Backend logic currently resides in `apiScripts.ts`, which contains reusable blocks (IPython and shell) triggered from the GUI. These scripts:

- Install and launch Scaphandre and Prometheus (in-pod agent)
- Query system metrics
- Collect timestamps and metadata
- Store energy logs and generate experiment IDs
- Send experiment metadata to remote external FDMI (D4Science)

This setup can be further exposed as separate functionality through a structured API endpoint to decouple frontend-backend communication and allow external triggers.

Figure 6: EcoJupyter pipeline diagram

4.5 Reproducible Experiment Design Extension

Reproducibility, as motivated in Section 2.3, is a key to sustainability. The Reproducible Experiment Design Extension accesses lower layer RI elements to provide researchers and researcher tools with the capability to create reproducible experiment workflows. The interaction with lower-layer RI elements is described as follows:

- **Storage:** Most experimental workflows require some sort of permanent storage access. Different RIs offer different solutions. For example, EGI's grid computing infrastructure allows to access distributed file systems such as dCache, STORM and EOS. Other RIs offer object storage, with industry standard S3-APIs. Besides in-memory filesystems, SLICES-RI includes option to mount network filesystems or access block storage or volumes directly.
- **Resource reservation and allocation:** Reproducibility is enabled by different researchers having access to the same infrastructure. RIs need resource reservation and allocation mechanisms to enable it. There are different approaches from different RIs for this problem. This concept is a prerequisite to establish data provenance and data management as actions on the RI become tractable to individual users and allocations. Also, brokering logic to place experiments on resource optimal infrastructure needs such mechanisms. The SLICES-RI blueprint—for now—uses a simple calendar based system. Other RIs such as EGI use job schedulers. Again, others use cloud tooling such as OpenStack for resource reservation and allocation.
- **Resource initialisation:** Part of the reproducibility approach is to define and guarantee a defined state of software systems involved in the experiment. Depending on the RI, different approaches are needed to achieve this goal of isolating independent experiment runs from each other. Defined and automated resource initialisation is a prerequisite for subsequent automation tools. All related files of the experiment need to be brought into an initial state, and all relevant software systems must be initialised. In practice, different solutions are needed for container-based, virtualisation-based, or bare-metal resources.
- **Task and workflow automation primitives:** RIs must provide primitives for task and workflow automation. Depending on the scope of the RI, different approaches are needed. In the case several nodes are involved in an experiment, inter-node synchronisation methods are helpful to design distributed experiment workflows. Another building block is synchronous or asynchronous task scheduling and command execution. Pos and cwl are two domain-specific examples for such solutions. Other general purpose tools partially covering this problem area are Kubernetes, Ansible, or simple shell scripts. There exist various domain specific solutions.

Section 5.1 describes a Jupyter-based VRE extension for accessing and controlling the aforementioned RI functionalities.

4.6 GreenDIGIT Federated Data Management Infrastructure

Integration of the Federated Data Management Infrastructure (FDMI) is a key part of the VRE, allowing for the publication of research artifacts enriched with metadata in a structured and findable way.

4.6.1 Design and Functional Components

The FDMI is a flexible and extensible system built upon the SoBigData e-infrastructure provider D4Science. It has been extended to support a diverse, community-driven, and expandable range of data asset types, e.g. experiments.

Figure 7: FDMI reference architecture

Figure 7 illustrates the reference architecture of the FDMI, designed and operated to meet the needs of the GreenDIGIT project. It comprises the following main components:

- (a) the Web User Interface, which provides users with an intuitive environment to browse, search, and interact with catalogue contents, based on the CKAN open-source technology;
- (b) the Representational State Transfer API (RESTful API), enabling programmatic access to the FDMI capabilities for querying and publishing metadata records;
- (c) the FDMI Service, responsible for the storage, indexing, and management of metadata, as well as coordination across infrastructure components, based on the D4Science Catalogue Service gCat;
- (d) the Metadata Profiles, which define the structure, semantics, and validation constraints for the various types of resources that can be published through the infrastructure.

The actual payloads of the items catalogued may be referenced via persistent URLs or directly stored within the Storage Infrastructure, typically in a designated area of the SoBigData Workspace ensuring interoperability and support for reproducible research.

Figure 8 illustrates the data model supported by the FDMI, designed and operated to serve the needs of the GreenDIGIT project. The model defines how each data item is structured and described through metadata, ensuring consistent management and discoverability across the infrastructure.

Each published item within the FDMI includes common metadata fields, profile specific fields, and links to shared resources.

Common metadata fields, which are shared across all item types, regardless of their specific content. These include:

- a unique identifier,
- a title,
- a description,
- a set of tags,

- a license,
- a visibility flag (defining whether the item is publicly visible or restricted to specific users, such as members of a VRE ,
- the author,
- the maintainer, and
- the associated metadata profile, which determines the item-specific metadata structure.

Figure 8: FDMI data model

Metadata profile-based fields, which provide detailed and type-specific information depending on the nature of the item. Each Metadata Profile defines:

- the field name,
- whether the field is mandatory or optional,
- the data type (e.g., string, text, boolean, number, timestamp, time interval),
- the cardinality (i.e. whether the field can have multiple values),
- any default value,
- a description or help note to assist users in data entry,
- any associated controlled vocabulary, and
- any validation rule to ensure correct data input.

Links to resources, representing the actual payloads referenced or stored. Each resource is described by:

- a resource identifier,
- the URL where it is located,
- a name,
- a description, and

- the file format (e.g., ZIP, XML, JSON).

This structured approach facilitates rich metadata description, improves interoperability across domains, and supports effective data sharing and reuse.

Figure 9 presents an example snippet of a Metadata Profile encoded in eXtensible Markup Language (XML). Each profile defines a specific item typology and consists of a structured list of metadata field specifications. These specifications not only describe the characteristics of the item-specific metadata fields (such as name, type, multiplicity, etc.), but may also include two optional directives aimed at enhancing automation and consistency:

The tagging directive enables the FDMI to automatically generate a tag within the item's common metadata, based on the value provided in that specific field.

The group management directive allows the FDMI to dynamically associate the item with a defined group, again determined by the value assigned to the corresponding metadata field.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<metadataFormat type="YOUR TYPE HERE">
  <metadataField categoryref="category_id_#">
    <fieldId>ID of Metadata Field that identifies the field name in the Document (stored in the Service)</fieldId>
    <fieldName>Name of Metadata Field</fieldName>
    <mandatory>true|false</mandatory>
    <dataType>String|Time|Time_Interval|Times_ListOf|Text|Boolean|Number|GeoJSON</dataType>
    <maxOccurs>N|*</maxOccurs>
    <defaultValue>default value</defaultValue>
    <note>[the note is shown as a suggestion in the insert/update metadata form of Catalogue Publisher Widget]
    </note>
    <vocabulary isMultiSelection="true|false">
      <vocabularyField>field1</vocabularyField>
      <vocabularyField>field2</vocabularyField>
      <vocabularyField>field3</vocabularyField>
    </vocabulary>
    <validator>
      <regularExpression>a regular expression for validating values</regularExpression>
    </validator>
    <tagging create="true|false" separator="char_to_separate">onFieldName|onValue|onFieldName_onValue|onValue_onFieldName</tagging>
    <grouping create="true|false">onFieldName|onValue|onFieldName_onValue|onValue_onFieldName</grouping>
  </metadataField>
</metadataFormat>
```

Figure 9: Example snippet of a Metadata Profile definition in XML

In essence, the Metadata Profile acts as a template for defining how information is captured, organised, and categorised across the infrastructure, supporting interoperability and streamlined data publishing.

Figure 10 and Figure 11 depict two screenshots of the FDMI web user interface based on CKAN. It allows its users to browse through the contents, search for specific items, and access every item of interest with its related resources. Moreover, it offers a user-friendly interface for allowing authorised users to manage contents: create new items, edit existing items, and remove items.

Figure 10: The FDMI web user interface

Figure 11: The FDMI catalogue listing

4.6.2 FDMI Integration with RESTful API

The GreenDIGIT VRE is designed to streamline the research process, and a key aspect of this is the automated publishing of research artifacts through integration with the Federated Data Management Infrastructure (FDMI). The VRE is designed to provide suitable building blocks to facilitate this, specifically by offering robust structured data and metadata handling capabilities.

As positioned on Layer 4 of the GreenDIGIT VRE architecture (which itself is based on the Jupyter ecosystem), the VRE incorporates several extensions. One crucial extension is the FDMI integration building block and according FDMI API.

This integrated approach means that researchers using the GreenDIGIT VRE benefit from a fully automated process for publishing experimental artifacts. By simplifying scientific exchange through automatic metadata handling and publishing, the VRE significantly enhances the reproducibility and sustainability goals of the GreenDIGIT project.

The FDMI RESTful API¹⁵ provides comprehensive programmatic access to its capabilities. It enables external systems and users to interact with it in a structured and automated way, supporting both querying and publishing operations. At its core, the FDMI Service (gCat)¹⁶ handles the storage,

¹⁵<https://api.d4science.org/catalogue/api-docs/ui/index.html>

¹⁶<https://code-repo.d4science.org/gCubeSystem/gcat>

indexing, and overall management of metadata records, while also coordinating interactions across the broader infrastructure ecosystem.

Through the gCat API, users can perform full CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations across key metadata collections, including:

- the Item Collection, which holds all items;
- the Resource Collection, containing the resources associated with each item;
- the Profile Collection, defining the metadata structure for different item types;
- the Namespace Collection, used to organise and scope metadata entities;
- the License Collection, providing standardised license options for catalogued content;
- and the Trash Collection, storing items marked for deletion but not yet purged.

The screenshot displays the Swagger UI for the gCube Catalogue (gCat) Service. At the top, the Swagger logo and the URL `https://api.d4science.org/catalogue/api-docs/ui/swagger.json` are visible. The service title is **gCube Catalogue (gCat) Service 2.6.0**, with a base URL of `/gcat`. Below the title, there is a welcome message and a link to a wiki page. The main content is organized into three sections:

- Configuration APIs**: This section is titled "The catalogue configuration for the context of the request". It lists five endpoints:
 - POST `/configurations`
 - DELETE `/configurations/{CONTEXT_FULLNAME_PARAMETER}`
 - GET `/configurations/{CONTEXT_FULLNAME_PARAMETER}`
 - PATCH `/configurations/{CONTEXT_FULLNAME_PARAMETER}`
 - PUT `/configurations/{CONTEXT_FULLNAME_PARAMETER}`
- Group APIs**: This section is titled "This concept is mutated by Ckan which is used as underlying technology to persist items." It lists six endpoints:
 - GET `/groups`
 - POST `/groups`
 - DELETE `/groups/{GROUP_ID}`
 - GET `/groups/{GROUP_ID}`
 - PATCH `/groups/{GROUP_ID}`
 - PUT `/groups/{GROUP_ID}`
- Item APIs**: This section is titled "Item is a set of metadata to describe a concept." It lists seven endpoints:
 - DELETE `/items`
 - GET `/items`
 - POST `/items`
 - DELETE `/items/{ITEM_ID}`
 - GET `/items/{ITEM_ID}`
 - PATCH `/items/{ITEM_ID}`
 - POST `/items/{ITEM_ID}`
 - PUT `/items/{ITEM_ID}`

Figure 12: FDMI RESTful API interactive interface

FDMI administrators additionally have access to privileged operations on collections such as Groups, Organisations, Users, and Configuration settings, enabling granular control over access policies, user roles, and catalogue behaviour.

This robust and extensible API framework ensures seamless metadata integration and governance across the VRE ecosystem. The presented FDMI and API design provides a basis for compatibility and integration with the SLICES Data Management Infrastructure [2].

5 Prototype Implementation of the Virtual Research Environment Extensions for Reproducible, Sustainable, and Open Science

In this chapter, VRE extensions are described. They extend Jupyter-based VREs with reproducible experiment design capabilities, environmental impact assessment dashboards, and automated FDMI publishing. In the first sub-chapter we describe a mapping implementation from pos framework into Jupyter notebook. In the second we describe the EcoJupyter design, implementation and system deployed. Both use the RO-Crate as their packaging metadata approach, although their use-case differs.

5.1 Reproducible Experiment Design Extension for a Virtual Research Environment

The development of the SLICES RI is driven by the various communities using the infrastructure. As each scientific community has their own set of requirements, tools, and way to measure flexibility of the RI is highly important. The same holds also for the other infrastructures participating in GreenDIGIT. Previous sections already described how Jupyter notebooks are used as a common way between the infrastructures to define, execute, evaluate, and document experiments.

The workflow described in the following, is currently used by the SLICES-RI Post 5G BluePrint. There, pos ensures the reproducibility of experiments relying on a full automation of the experiment from setup to measurements and finally the evaluation of experiments. However, as part of GreenDIGIT this workflow was adapted to become more flexible and also support other platforms.

In this section, we describe how we adapted the pos workflow to support Jupyter notebooks and other testbed orchestrators. The concept is based on a journal paper released in June 2025 [27]. One of the contributions of this paper is the mapping of the pos workflow to Jupyter notebooks. Automation is key to achieving reproducibility; therefore, the different scripts that define the experiment workflow need to be mapped to a Jupyter notebook. The pos workflow relies on different phases (setup, measurement, and evaluation) and different roles the nodes can take (e.g., load generator or device under test). Each of these phases and each different role is typically defined in a separate script. Besides the scripts, there are also files that define the variables used to parameterise the experiment, e.g. the number of input parameters that should be investigated. The separation into phases, roles and scripts/variables defines the structure of the pos experiment. The separation in phases and roles allows an easy navigation of the experiment for people familiar with the experiment. The separation between variables and scripts simplifies the modification of the experiments. By simply editing the variables files an experiment can be modified without touching the actual code. All of these scripts are mapped to separate cells of the Jupyter notebook. Therefore, the Jupyter notebook contains all scripts, variable definitions while maintaining the original structure that defines the experiment.

The clear purpose of each of the different files/cells that makes up the structure of the experiment workflow has several advantages. It helps experimenters familiar with the workflow to easily understand the different parts of the experiment. It also simplifies the modification of existing experiments. Additionally, it creates a template to create own experiments based on other experiments. An example of this structure in a Jupyter notebook can be found here¹⁷.

Originally pos was designed to orchestrate testbeds and control experiments. Both functions were integrated into a monolithic testbed software. This meant that the pos workflow could only be used on testbeds that were running the entire testbed software. It was not possible to use the reproducible workflow on other testbeds with different controllers. To solve this issue, the pos software was refactored and split into two parts, the testbed orchestrator and the experiment controller. The result is shown in Figure 13 and Figure 14.

Figure 13: Step 1 of pos split architecture: Testbed orchestrator preparing experiment nodes

Figure 14: Step 2 of pos split architecture: Experiment controller performing experiment

¹⁷<https://github.com/gallenmu/pos-jupyter/blob/main/pos-experiment.ipynb>

There the testbed orchestrator allocates the experiment nodes that execute the experiment. After preparing the experiment nodes, e.g., rebooting the nodes and providing secure access, the experiment controller takes over to ensure the reproducible execution of the experiment. The experiment controller is the main component responsible to ensure reproducibility. By porting the experiment controller to a different testbed, also other testbeds can execute pos workflows and profit from its reproducibility feature. We successfully demonstrated this when porting an experiment from the pos testbed to the CloudLab and Chameleon testbed [28].

5.2 Impact Assessment Dashboards

Virtual Research Environment (VREs) provide digital platforms, which are crucial for enabling collaboration, data sharing, and experimental management in research; particularly in scientific research contexts, through RI. RIs significantly enhance computational performance that allows for research endeavours to be successful. However, they similarly elevate energy consumption at scale—revealing the need for tools that give researchers the information, ability and pro-activeness for informed decisions for managing the carbon footprint of their workloads, with minimal hassle. Such tools align with GreenDIGIT’s mission and recommendations for reducing carbon emissions in RIs.

Existing sustainability-focused tools

Several existing tools aim to measure and optimise usage and carbon emissions. Such tools are, for example:

CarbonScaler [29] estimates carbon emissions specifically related to data centre and cloud infrastructures, utilising data-driven modelling techniques to inform decisions for energy optimisation.

Zeus [30] focuses explicitly on deep learning workloads, providing cherry-picked energy profiling, optimisation through model pruning and quantisation, and visualisation dashboards to report findings.

While these tools provide robust foundational insights towards sustainability, their general-purpose orientation severely limits their applicability and effectiveness for the particular requirements of research—which typically requires High-Performance Computing (HPC) RIs. Moreover, the sustainability metrics these tools generate often lack reproducibility when applied in different environments or under varied conditions. EcoJupyter addresses this by coupling energy measurements with experiment metadata reproducibility, ensuring that both metrics and the experimental context can be reliably reproduced, interpreted, and compared across distinct infrastructures and environments.

Although the aforementioned tools effectively handle broad categories of workloads, they lack specific focus necessary to address challenges in RIs and HPC. Such infrastructures and workloads, such as intensive microbiology analysis, intensive machine learning computations or large-scale simulations, demand precise energy management strategies. General-purpose sustainability-focused

tools typically do not provide detailed granularity and adaptability required for those scenarios. The need for the development of a framework that leverages those capabilities adapted to the nature of such workloads is paramount to significantly reduce its carbon footprint. Similarly, these tools rarely capture the experimental context in a structured, standardised form—limiting the ability to reproduce, compare, or reuse sustainability metrics (and other metadata) across different systems, setups, or research environments.

5.2.1 EcoJupyter: Platform-Agnostic Pluggable RI tool for Impact Assessment in Jupyter Workflows

We propose EcoJupyter as a framework: a platform-agnostic pluggable RI tool. This is a plug-in developed as a Jupyter-based extension, and as an environment-agnostic and easily integrable into existing research workflows, environments and infrastructures. The goal of this tool is to help the researcher achieve a more aware and informed decision when computing its workloads—and to replicate environment and results easily across different RIs.

The tool is designed to provide predictive, real-time, and actionable insights into energy usage and carbon emissions through clearly defined and meaningful KPIs. Additionally, it integrates automated reproducibility capabilities, producing FAIR-compliant reports about the **workflow** and **experiment** execution, while publishing its details in an external FDML.

5.2.1.1 Energy Estimation and Access Mechanisms

Scaphandre¹⁸ operates by reading Intel RAPL counters available in modern processors. It uses the powercap sysfs interface to expose values such as package energy, DRAM energy, and core frequency data. Scaphandre can run as a standalone agent or in sidecar mode within a Kubernetes pod, exporting data to Prometheus endpoints.

Prometheus¹⁹ is used as the timeseries database that collects metrics exposed by agents such as Scaphandre. It periodically scrapes HTTP endpoints that serve metrics in OpenMetrics²⁰ format. Prometheus stores these data points with timestamps, enabling temporal queries and visualisations.

Together, these tools provide a scalable, low-overhead architecture for ingesting, storing, and analysing sustainability-relevant data within RIs.

5.2.1.2 Metrics Exported by Scaphandre

Scaphandre exports a set of hardware-level metrics related to energy and CPU state. These include:

```
scaph_energy_joules  
scaph_energy_microjoules  
scaph_host_energy_mjoules_total
```

¹⁸ <https://github.com/hubblo-org/scaphandre>

¹⁹ <https://prometheus.io/>

²⁰ https://prometheus.io/docs/specs/om/open_metrics_spec/


```
scaph_package_energy_mjoules_total  
scaph_dram_energy_mjoules_total  
scaph_core_energy_mjoules_total  
scaph_cpu_frequency_hertz  
scaph_cpu_cstate_seconds_total  
scaph_cpu_pstate_seconds_total  
scaph_power_microwatts  
scaph_component_energy_ujoules_total
```

These values can be aggregated and filtered by container, user, or workload session to support analysis and accountability in energy consumption and carbon footprint.

5.2.1.3 Visualisation of Metrics

Once metrics are exposed via Prometheus endpoints, they can be visualised using any tool capable of processing time-series data. In our implementation, we integrated a custom visualisation layer built with **Material UI (MUI) charts**²¹ within a **React**²² based front-end, embedded directly into the JupyterLab extension. This setup allows for lightweight, responsive, and customisable dashboard adapted to the researcher's experiment context. The charts display key energy and performance metrics over time, offering both real-time updates and historical views within the notebook environment.

²¹ <https://mui.com/x/react-charts/>

²² <https://react.dev/>

Figure 15: Real-time metrics visualisation

As an alternative or complementary solution, we recommend **Grafana**²³, a widely adopted platform that offers advanced visualisation, alerting, and dashboarding capabilities for Prometheus data. Grafana remains a popular and consistent option for system administrators and infrastructure managers who require a centralised overview of timeseries data.

Visual dashboards—whether embedded or external—not only support reporting and analysis but also act as behavioural nudges, making the sustainability implications of researchers’ workflows more apparent and easier to interpret (Figure 15).

5.2.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for Sustainability Monitoring

As part of the EcoJupyter framework, a design decision was to provide researchers with *abstractions* that translate raw system-level metrics into meaningful, human-readable indicators. While raw readings from Scaphandre or other agents (e.g., CPU frequency, energy joules) offer high precision, their direct interpretability is limited for the average researcher. Instead, presenting KPIs offers a layer of semantic aggregation that aligns more closely with research goals, reproducibility concerns, and sustainability awareness.

²³ <https://grafana.com/>

These KPIs allow for meaningful comparison across experiments, users, and infrastructures, while enabling lightweight integration into research workflows. They can also be linked back to experiment reports and metadata standards such as RO-Crate, ensuring FAIR compliance and long-term utility.

5.2.2.1 Scientific and Conceptual Foundations: GSF, SCI, and the Impact Framework

The KPIs selected in EcoJupyter are inspired by the **Green Software Foundation’s (GSF)**²⁴ methodology and the **Software Carbon Intensity (SCI)**²⁵ specification. The GSF promotes practical and standardised ways of measuring and improving the sustainability of software systems, including cloud-native environments. Similarly, the SCI metric provides a normalised carbon impact measure per unit of software activity.

EcoJupyter also draws inspiration from the **Impact Framework**²⁶, which provides a model for structuring and evaluating sustainability contributions in RIs. This framework underlines the importance of aligning measurement with policy goals, stakeholder requirements, and domain-specific functional units—an approach that directly shaped our selection and definition of the following four KPIs.

5.2.2.2 Selected KPIs and Their Formulas

EcoJupyter defines and showcases a set of sustainability KPIs to help researchers to better interpret energy usage and emissions in context. These indicators are computed from Prometheus metrics and represented inside the JupyterLab extension interface using a React dashboard (MUI).

In the context of EcoJupyter, *unit* refers to a *functional unit of work* associated with a given experiment. This is an inferred quantity that represents the scientific “output” or scope of the experiment. For our use-case we must use a simplified definition of the indicator as described below:

Functional Unit (R)=Total output size (in MB)

While domain-specific units and operations (e.g., “rows processed”, “images classified”) provide a more granular insight, they introduce ambiguity and require domain specification and instrumentation. Future versions might include this sort of complementary indicators; however, the current implementation prioritises robustness and clarity.

1. Software Carbon Intensity (SCI)

$$SCI = \frac{E * I + M}{R}$$

E = Total energy consumed in kWh

I = Carbon intensity of the energy grid (gCO₂/kWh)

M = Embodied emissions of infrastructure (gCO₂)

R = Functional unit of work

²⁴ <https://greensoftware.foundation/>

²⁵ <https://sci-guide.greensoftware.foundation/>

²⁶ <https://if.greensoftware.foundation/>

Context: SCI contextualises both immediate and hidden environmental impacts. It is useful for researchers working across different hardware settings, as it accounts for infrastructure lifecycle emissions in addition to energy consumption.

2. Energy per Unit

$$Energy/U = \frac{E}{R}$$

E: Total Energy Consumed (in joules)

R: Functional Unit of Work

Context: This KPI indicates how much energy is required to perform a single unit of work. It is particularly useful in comparing the efficiency of experiments or workloads regardless of their size or duration. The prototype implementation uses Wh for readability.

3. Operational Emissions

$$O = E \cdot I$$

- **E:** Total Energy Consumed
- **I:** Carbon Intensity of electricity (kg CO₂e/kWh)

Context: This KPI is useful for basic carbon footprint estimates where infrastructure manufacturing is not relevant or cannot be accurately captured.

Calculation Flow

1. **Metrics ingestion** from agents (e.g. `scaph_energy_joules`, `scaph_cpu_frequency_hertz`)
2. **Energy aggregation** during notebook runtime using Prometheus queries
3. **Functional Unit estimation**, either user-defined (via metadata or RO-Crate) or inferred (output MB)
4. **Carbon intensity** either taken from configured grid values or queried dynamically via external APIs
5. **KPI formulas** evaluated in real-time and stored/exported with metadata

These KPIs are exported in human-readable summaries, JSON records, and optionally attached to the experiment's RO-Crate for downstream usage by external FDMI infrastructures (e.g., SoBigData).

5.2.3 Reproducibility, repeatability and portability implementation

5.2.3.1 Concepts from the 4-Pillar Framework

The conceptual foundations of EcoJupyter align directly with the **4-Pillar Conceptual Reproducibility Framework** (Section 3.1), adapting its principles to Jupyter-based VREs. This section revisits key concepts—*Workflow*, *Experiment*, and *Lifecycle*—to clarify their role in this empirical experiment for reproducibility and sustainability within GreenDIGIT.

Workflow and Experiment in Jupyter Context

Within EcoJupyter, the **workflow** is operationalised as the Jupyter Notebook itself—a complete, executable record of a computational process. Each **experiment** corresponds to a bounded execution instance within a notebook, determined by the execution of a defined cell sequence (e.g., from first to last cell). This mapping allows automated extraction of experiment boundaries, metadata, and metrics, supporting Pillar 1 (Conceptual Definition) and Pillar 2 (Design & Deployment).

Metric Collection and Monitoring

As per Pillar 3 (Execution & Measurement), EcoJupyter integrates real-time metric collection during experiment execution. This includes automated triggers to initiate energy monitoring agents such as Scaphandre, and structured logging of metrics relevant for sustainability KPIs. These metrics are synchronised with experiment identifiers and timestamps, enabling reproducibility and comparability in different environments and RIs.

Lifecycle and Reproducibility

Pillar 4 (Preservation & Publication) is addressed by bundling each experiment’s outputs—code, results, environment, and metrics—into a standardised, RO-Crate-compliant folder structure. This allows seamless export, reuse, and publication in federated data infrastructures. Lifecycle support is limited to reproducible “batch” experiments (not exploratory usage), ensuring consistency in metric interpretation and sustainability reporting.

Reproducibility, *repeatability*, and *portability* are essential to the EcoJupyter’s architecture and goals—as mentioned by the “4-Pillar Conceptual Reproducibility Framework”. To achieve the latter in heterogeneous and federated infrastructures, EcoJupyter implements two core layers of interoperability:

- **Experiment Metadata:** Captured internally using the RO-Crate standard, ensuring FAIR-aligned documentation of experiment context, results, and sustainability metrics.
- **FDMI Submission Mechanism:** Provides an external-facing, API-based mechanism for publishing experiments to federated data infrastructures (e.g., SoBigData), allowing integration with FAIR-compliant platforms such as EOSC and Zenodo.

The corresponding diagram (Figure 16) illustrates this dual-layer model, showing how experiments transition from local execution to structured export and publication.

Figure 16: Experiment 2-Layered model (FDMI and metrics)

These components work in tandem to automate end-of-workflow metadata generation, triggered when a Jupyter notebook reaches its final cell. By aligning the RO-Crate structure and FDMI metadata keys, EcoJupyter maximises reusability and simplifies programmatic submission.

5.2.3.2 In-Experiment Metadata: RO-Crate

The **RO-Crate** format is used internally to describe each experiment's complete lifecycle. Generated automatically at the end of a workflow, the RO-Crate structure packages all key artifacts: logs, energy metrics, configuration, environment, and output files. This aligns with the FAIR data principles mentioned in Chapter 2.1.

Example folder structure:

```

experiment-xyz-ro-crate/
├── ro-crate-metadata.json # FAIR metadata + sustainability extensions
├── data/
│   ├── energy_data.csv # Versioned energy, carbon footprint data
│   └── experiment_results.h5
├── logs/
│   └── energy_log.json # Energy data: Versioned/by experiment
├── workflow/
│   ├── workflow.cwl
│   ├── Jupyter
│   └── Shell_script
└── environment/
  
```



```
├── Dockerfile
├── sw_libraries
├── experiment_setup/
│   ├── Deployment_platform_template # (Ansible, Terraform, K8s, CF)
│   ├── Configuration_script
│   ├── test_generator
│   │   └── test_sequence
│   └── sensor_measurement_equipment
├── lifecycle-analysis/
│   └── lca-report.pdf
└── README.md
```

Some RO-Crate values (e.g. energy logs, Experiment ID, platform info) overlap with FDMI metadata, ensuring consistency across internal and external views of the experiment. This dual packaging approach supports both runtime reproducibility and structured publication pipelines.

After each workflow execution, EcoJupyter automatically compiles and exports all relevant (meta)data into a structured RO-Crate package. This includes the `ro-crate-metadata.json` file, runtime logs and energy metrics, environment specifications (e.g., platform details, setup scripts), the original Jupyter notebook (`.ipynb`), and lifecycle assessment outputs. This complete snapshot ensures that each experiment is transparently documented, reproducible, and ready for publication or reuse across federated RIs.

Implementation in the prototype

While the structural logic for reproducibility and portability has been implemented in EcoJupyter, several functional aspects are still under development. Currently, RO-Crate metadata is correctly generated at the end of each workflow execution, including sustainability-related components such as energy logs and runtime environment descriptors. However, the platform does not yet support full sharing or automated publication through permanent links. This capability—such as generating a persistent URL or submission to a FDMI catalogue—is intended for future development. Additionally, the current implementation supports a minimal set of metadata fields, with several fields in the RO-Crate left as placeholders to be populated in later iterations (e.g., author identifiers, software dependencies, and execution provenance). Nonetheless, the foundation for structured export and reproducible packaging is operational.

The following features have been successfully implemented so far:

- Generation of a structured RO-Crate folder for each experiment, with all relevant directories automatically created (e.g., `workflow/`, `logs/`, `data/`, `environment/`, `experiment_setup/`).

Auto-creation of `ro-crate-metadata.json` with contextual references to the Jupyter notebook and experiment components.

- Logging of session-level energy metrics into structured files (currently placeholder-based).
- Triggering of metadata generation and packaging upon execution of final notebook cell.
- Creation of a reproducible ZIP archive containing all experiment artifacts and metadata.

- Alignment between RO-Crate output and the FDMI submission schema (preparing for automated submission via REST API).

These elements ensure that each experiment is properly encapsulated and reproducible by design, while also preparing the ground for future integration with external sharing and publication mechanisms.

An example snippet from the automatically generated RO-Crate metadata JSON file can be found in Appendix D.

5.2.3.3 FDMI Implementation

Within the EcoJupyter tool, FDMI integration enables seamless and automatic publication of experiment objects and metadata (RO-Crate) into federated environments, such as the SoBigData (D4Science) catalogue. Each submission adheres to the metadata schema agreed upon within GreenDIGIT partners (see Appendix B)—structured around key-value pairs and a `Bearer-`authenticated API for implicit security.

API Request Structure Concepts

A typical request includes the following HTTP request characteristics:

- A POST operation to:
`https://api.d4science.org/gcat/items`
- A Bearer token, retrievable from the FDMI prototype's homepage (greendigit.d4science.org) (Section 3.3.2)
- A JSON body with required fields such as `Experiment ID`, `Project ID`, `Session reading metrics`, and `system:type`: "Experiment"

Figure 17: Bearer token UI

A typical request is done through a shell script integrating all of these components (see Appendix A).

It respects **OGC Web Processing Service (WPS)**²⁷ principles for interoperable geospatial and experimental workflows, with a metadata model extensible via `extras`. This submission model is designed to be **pluggable**, enabling future extensions to **EOSC**²⁸, **Zenodo**²⁹, or other WPS-compliant infrastructures.

Influences and derivation of data model from RO-Crate

The integration of both RO-Crate metadata (concerning the **experiment** and **workflow**) and the FDMI submission mechanism forms a pivotal connection between in-notebook reproducibility and its federated publication. EcoJupyter leverages its RO-Crate output automatically to generate its metadata and a valid FDMI-compatible payload. This ensures metadata consistency and reduces redundancy in configuration effort from researchers.

Metadata Mapping and Reuse

A number of metadata fields defined in the RO-Crate structure map directly to keys used in the FDMI submission—namely in the `extras` field. These shared fields include:

RO-Crate Metadata Element	FDMI Key (<code>extras</code>)
Environment OS (<code>environment/</code>)	"Environment OS"
Platform (<code>ro-crate-metadata.json</code>)	"Environment Platform"
Programming language (e.g., Python)	"Programming Language"
Experiment identifier (UUID/timestamp)	"Experiment ID"
GreenDIGIT node or execution host	"GreenDIGIT Node"
Project identifier (if declared)	"Project ID"
Creator metadata (author/ORCID)	"Creator", "Creator Email", "Creator Name PI"

The overlap ensures that once the workflow completes and a RO-Crate is generated, a significant portion of the FDMI submission body can be automatically inferred—reducing manual input from the researcher.

²⁷ <https://www.ogc.org/standards/wps/>

²⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/>

Session Reading Metrics

A particular field introduced and adapted particularly from the EcoJupyter use-case and needs due to its cross-platform sustainability analysis focus is:

“**Session reading metrics**”: This contains the *time-bounded* output of energy and system metrics collected during an experiment from a particular workflow. These readings are generated based on the system-defined start and end timestamps—which are correlated with the first and last cell execution of the Jupyter Notebook workflow. These readings include aggregated metrics from agents such as Scaphandre and allow each submission to encapsulate its environmental footprint into a reusable and standard format.

FDMI Resources field

Beyond metadata, the FDMI API also supports a field with the key `resources`. This is used to attach heavier attached artifacts—which in EcoJupyter use-case and context includes a ZIP folder with the following content:

- RO-Crate metadata JSON; and
- Assets included in the experiment, as specified in the metadata JSON file.

```
"resources": [  
  {  
    "name": "experiment-123-time",  
    "url": "https://greendigit-server.node/experiment-123-time",  
    "format": "zip"  
  }  
]
```

By using this structure, we ensure metadata preservation and reproducibility while also linking external objects that can be used directly. Moreover, we provide that the tool aligns with OGC WPS standards and with FAIR principles of *Accessibility* and *Reusability*.

5.2.4 Implementing metric collection and a visualisation dashboard

The EcoJupyter extension was designed to offer a seamless, low-effort interface for sustainability monitoring and reproducibility within notebook-based workflows. The plugin interface allows researchers to interact with metrics and metadata in real-time, without requiring manual setup or external tools.

5.2.4.1 User Interface and Design Decisions

The plugin interface was built with simplicity in mind, with the following main control features:

- **Refresh button**: Triggers manual retrieval of Prometheus metrics. Useful for immediate updates when experimenting with live workloads.
- **Export button**: Packages the current experiment’s artifacts—metrics, environment info, and notebook context—into a RO-Crate-compliant folder.

- **Submit to FDMI:** Wraps up the RO-Crate (and other content) and sends it to the federated data infrastructure (e.g., SoBigData) via a RESTful API.
- **Dropdown selectors:** Let the user specify which experiment and workflow to focus on, enabling targeted metric collection and export.

Figure 18: EcoJupyter main view

Each of these elements invokes notebook-level commands through Jupyter's `IKernelConnection.executeRequest()` API. This approach avoids external dependencies and remains compatible with most JupyterLab environments, contributing to the plugin's portability and minimal setup overhead.

The visual interface presents two key components: a KPI display showing three sustainability indicators—*Energy per Unit*, *Software Carbon Intensity (SCI)*, and *Operational Emissions*—and a real-time metrics panel with four default charts tracking system performance during active workflows.

KPI display

The dashboard offers three sustainability indicators that form the core of EcoJupyter’s monitoring layer: *Energy per Unit*, *Software Carbon Intensity (SCI)*, and *Operational Emissions*. These metrics offer immediate, interpretable feedback on both the energy efficiency and carbon impact of an experiment, whether during live execution or in retrospective analysis. By translating low-level telemetry into concise, actionable KPIs, the interface removes cognitive overhead while supporting a more informed, sustainability-aware experimentation.

Real-time metrics collection and visualisation

EcoJupyter retrieves experiment-specific energy and system metrics from the `prometheus-<user>/metrics` endpoint, offering both *automated* and *manual* update mechanisms. By default, the dashboard refreshes every 15 seconds to provide continuous, real-time insight into system behaviour. Users may also trigger updates on demand via the refresh control. Visualisations are rendered through the MUI frontend framework, which includes charts embedded in the JupyterLab interface. This allows for more seamless, time-aligned tracking of resource usage while the workflow is being executed. The goal is to promote better awareness of computational impact and supports adaptive decision-making during experimentation.

5.2.4.2 Export and submission workflow

After completing a workflow, researchers can initiate the export process that generates a RO-Crate—an interoperable, FAIR-aligned package containing all relevant experiment metadata. This includes runtime metrics, software and environment configurations, execution boundaries, and any generated artifacts. Once created, the RO-Crate can be submitted directly to the FDMI (SoBigData) through an integrated HTTP API call. This ensures that the experiment is not only preserved with full contextual detail but also becomes a discoverable and reusable entry within the broader federated research ecosystem. More information and figures illustrating the export, submission, and publication of catalogue entries in the FDMI repository can be found in [Section Error! Reference source not found.5.3.3](#).

5.2.4.3 Installation

EcoJupyter is available as a Python package that can be installed through “pip”, and it can be easily installed on any instance of JupyterLab that can install Python package modules. More information about the usage, installation, and output can be found in Appendix C.

5.3 Automated Publishing

The end-to-end FDMI publication pipeline is natively embedded within the Jupyter environment as a dedicated “API Integration” notebook, thereby transforming each notebook execution into a fully reproducible and federated record. Upon completion of the analytical workflow, the researcher opens the integration notebook and is guided through two simple steps:

5.3.1 Prepare and Publish

The notebook first prompts the user to upload the RO-Crate ZIP from the experiment including the measured energy data into the workspace and supply their Bearer token. A screenshot of this is provided in Figure 19.

Step 1 - Upload your RO-Crate `.zip` to the Workspace

Before registering the dataset, you need to upload the RO-Crate `.zip` file manually to your Workspace.

1. Go to the GreenDIGIT VRE Workspace: -> <https://sobigdata.d4science.org/group/greendigit/workspace>
2. Upload your `.zip` RO-Crate to a folder (e.g. "MyResults")
3. After upload:
 - Click the file
 - Choose "Share"
 - Enable public access
 - Copy the **public link** to the file

This link is required in the next step.

Figure 19: Step 1 and Step 2 of user interface of automated publishing into FDMI.

Next, as depicted in Figure 20, it asks for the local path to the RO-Crate folder and, with a single command cell, finalises the RO-Crate export, bundles code, environment, logs and energy measurements into a JSON-LD package, and immediately issues the HTTP POST request to the FDMI endpoint.

Step 3 - Specify your local RO-Crate folder path

This should point to the uploaded (which you maybe zipped before uploading) RO-Crate **on your local system**.

If you are using the default GreenDIGIT example crate, you can simply **press Enter** to use the pre-filled path.

Figure 20: Step 3 of user interface of automated publishing into FDMI.

As soon as the POST returns, the notebook prints the public URL of the newly created catalogue entry, shown in Figure 21.


```
Extracting metadata from RO-Crate...  
Metadata extracted.
```

```
Publishing to GreenDIGIT catalogue (gCat)...  
Published successfully.
```

```
Your dataset is now available at:
```

```
https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/GreenDIGIT/moongen-example-experiment-with-energy-measurement
```

Figure 21: Final step of automated publishing into FDMI

5.3.2 Published Catalogue Entry (MARTE)

Organisation

GreenDIGIT

GreenDIGIT
GreenDIGIT provides researchers with a web-based platform to design and conduct reproducible experiments while promoting Open Science practices. It streamlines the entire... [read more](#)

License

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 [OPEN DATA](#)

Tags

energy measurements reproducibility

Data and Resources

 RO-Crate ZIP Archive [Explore](#)

Item URL

<https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/GreenDIGIT/moongen-example-experiment-with-energy-measurement>

Additional Info

Field	Value
Creation Date	2025-06-13
Creator	Kilian Warmuth
Creator Email	kilian.warmuth@tum.de
Creator Name PI (Principal Investigator)	Kilian Warmuth
Environment OS	Linux
Environment Platform	D4Science GreenDIGIT
Experiment Dependencies	none
Experiment ID	exp-green-digit-001
GreenDIGIT Node	D4Science Pisa
Programming Language	Python
Project ID	GD-T5.2
Session reading metrics	enabled
system:type	Experiment

Management Info

Field	Value
Author	Warmuth Kilian
Maintainer	Warmuth Kilian
State	active
Last Updated	27. Juni 2025, 15:56 (UTC+02:00)
Created	27. Juni 2025, 15:56 (UTC+02:00)

Figure 22 Example entry in the FDMI portal which was automatically published

Figure 22 shows

```

Extracting metadata from RO-Crate...
Metadata extracted.

Publishing to GreenDIGIT catalogue (gCat)...
Published successfully.

Your dataset is now available at:
https://data.d4science.org/ctlg/GreenDIGIT/moongen-example-experiment-with-energy-measurement

```

Figure 21: Final step of automated publishing into FDMI the FDMI portal view of the published metadata. Tags, linked resources (the RO-Crate ZIP archive), the public Item URL and all supplementary “extras” fields (e.g. experiment ID, creation date, node location) are displayed exactly as they were mapped from the RO-Crate.

5.3.3 Published Catalogue Entry (EcoJupyter)

EcoJupyter implements its own dedicated automated artefact publishing pipeline. Figure 23 show this automatically published object of one of the test experiments into the FDMI platform (D4Science). It contains all pertinent metadata regarding the published artefact, in particular the Session reading metrics and Extras, which correspondingly contain the experiment metrics and all experiment metadata, including the `ro-crate-metadata.json`. All remaining specifications can be found in Chapter 5.2.3.3.

	,0,0,0,0,0,,,1024000,2854912,0,,,,,,,,,,,,, ,0,0,0,0,0,,,1024000,2854912,0,,,,,,,,,,,,, ,0,0,0,0,0,,,1024000,2854912,0,,,,,,,,,,,,,
system:type	Experiment
Management Info	
Field	Value
Source	null
Author	Ferreira Gonalo
Maintainer	Ferreira Gonalo
Version	1
State	active
Last Updated	17 July 2025, 13:43 (UTC+02:00)
Created	3 July 2025, 16:53 (UTC+02:00)

Figure 23 EcoJupyter GreenDIGIT artefact automatic publishing

5.4 System Prototype Based on Reproducibility Framework

This section describes the *System Deployment* of EcoJupyter as this Work Package's (WP) reproducibility prototype tool based on the reproducibility framework developed in this Deliverable. In addition to the design specification provided in earlier sections, we document the production deployment, the operational access model, and the installation approach used. The chosen tool for the prototype validation was EcoJupyter.

5.4.1 Deployed Reproducibility Prototype instance

A deployed instance of the EcoJupyter prototype is available and served online as part of this WP implementation and early validation of reproducibility-related activities:

- **Service URL:** <https://greendigit-ecojupyter.sztaki.hu/>; and
- **Source code (infrastructure and deployment configuration):** <https://github.com/g-uva/L1EcoVRE>.

This deployed instance provides an operational baseline on which partners can subscribe, run and test their Experiment/Workflow reproducibility aspect within Jupyter Notebook. The current deployment has been used for early validation with RI infrastructure operators, and it will be further extended and validated in subsequent work in T7.3.

5.4.2 Scope and Role within Architecture

EcoJupyter is implemented as an L1 ("RDE, Experiment") prototype: it is designed to be installable by any RI partner on their own infrastructure (e.g., Kubernetes-based environments) and to provide a consistent user-facing VRE that can be integrated with GreenDIGIT's monitoring and sustainability services.

The deployment described above has been performed at SZTAKI as an early validation step. This validation confirms portability across RI environments and reduces integration risk and effort for later cross-RI roll-out. In T7.3, the prototype will be extended and evaluated further, including validation across multiple RI sites using a cross-RI validation framework.

To ensure alignment, the dependency on prior WPs is explicit:

- WP4 provides the architectural context and requirements for integrating monitoring, sustainability metrics, and federated services.
- WP5 provides the VRE design, reproducibility mechanisms, and user-level tooling, including EcoJupyter as the primary user-facing environment for experiment execution and packaging.

Characteristics present in the architecture chapters (WP4 deliverables) that affect monitoring interfaces, identity and access, federation responsibilities, or data management flows are reflected in the EcoJupyter integration description and configuration, and will be further developed/extended in subsequent related WPs.

5.4.3 Installation and onboarding for RI partners

The EcoJupyter prototype is structured so that an RI partner can install and operate it within their infrastructure with minimal disruption and integration effort, only subject to local policy and identity constraints. At a high-level, RI partner installation comprises:

1. **Deployment setup:** installation of the EcoJupyter environment (L1EcoVRE) on the partner's Kubernetes cluster (or equivalent orchestration environment), including its configuration values (storage classes, resource quotas, etc.).
2. **User environment provisioning:** enabling Jupyter Notebook server spawning and base images consistent with the partner's permitted software stack. This is realised through the L1EcoVRE Kubernetes-Helm JupyterHub configuration, which defines the spawner settings and approved base images for use servers.
3. **Operational monitoring hooks:** enabling the relevant service-level telemetry and logging required for operational observability and future sustainability KPI integration. This requires controlled access to host energy interfaces (e.g., RAPL/powercap kernel) from the relevant pods; so that agents like Scaphandre can collect energy signals and expose them for ingestion.

This technical approach and stack support gradual and agnostic integration: the prototype can be deployed first as a functional VRE, and later connected to additional GreenDIGIT services as the federation and monitoring interfaces stabilise.

5.4.4 RI Manager deployment process

EcoJupyter is designed to be deployable by RI managers as a portable, Kubernetes-based VRE. The reference deployment is provided through the L1EcoVRE repository, which includes the Helm values files and the minimal installation steps required to reproduce the deployment on an RI-managed cluster.

The deployment uses Helm to manage the JupyterHub installation and related Kubernetes resources. In the current reference instance, the primary configuration file is `jhub-config-local.yaml`: which provides a baseline setup where monitoring components can be enabled without tightly coupling the RI deployment to a specific observability stack. RI managers can follow the repository `README.md` file for the end-to-end steps (cluster prerequisites, Helm chart installation, and exposure/access configuration).

During cross-RI validation, we anticipate supporting multiple deployment “flavours”, depending on partner policies and operational preferences; namely: (1) a sidecar-based approach (agent spawned alongside user pods), and (2) an in-pod or local approach, with optional pre-configuration of Prometheus/Scaphandre. The current reference points to the flavour *without* Prometheus/Scaphandre pre-configured, so that RI sites can integrate EcoJupyter with their existing monitoring stack or adopt the project-provided defaults in agreement with partners. This installation is provided through a decoupled execution script that can be executed before or after the spawning of a pod containing an in-

stance of the Jupyter notebook. This script and all other information can be found in the [README .md](#) file in the reference repository.

5.4.5 Authentication and user registration model

In the current prototype deployment, user subscription is performed manually:

- An administrator creates a user entry (username).
- The user sets their own password during initial onboarding.

This approach was selected for rapid prototyping and controlled early validation of the reproducibility framework. For further RI adoption and reduced operational overhead, more scalable authentication patterns are recommended in a Kubernetes/JupyterHub context, such as:

- **Federated identity via OAuth2/OIDC** (e.g., institutional SSO, Keycloak, or RI-provided identity services) using JupyterHub authenticator modules.
- **Invitation-based onboarding** with admin approval (reduces open self-registration risk while keeping operational effort manageable).
- **External identity providers** commonly used in research infrastructures (where applicable), enabling consistent access control across partner sites.

These improvements can be adopted by each RI partner depending on their policy and identity stack, without changing the core EcoJupyter functionality.

5.4.6 Automated publication in Zenodo and DOI generation

Following the agreed reproducibility principles, for the publication a Zenodo integration and DOI generation is used. EcoJupyter provides the *user-facing workflow and packaging logic* (e.g., generation of a reproducibility package such as an RO-Crate bundle) and exposes the required integration hooks. Repository publication and Persistent Identifier (PID) creation and handing are handled through the SoBigData/D4Science Federated Data Management Infrastructure (FDMI).

The SoBigData FDMI provides the operational services and interfaces for publishing and managing research products (including the “Experiment” profile) through authenticated APIs and web interfaces. EcoJupyter therefore treats Zenodo and DOI issuance as an *external service responsibility* and only implements the minimum client-side actions needed to request publication and receive the DOI/record handle required for later referencing and reporting.

Noise/spam reduction and “publishable” promotion workflow

Because EcoJupyter may generate a large number of experimental records (including intermediate runs that are not intended for wide dissemination), we adopt a simple two-stage approach to reduce “community noise”:

- **Stage A (default):** experiments are deposited within a SoBigData-managed space (working area), allowing frequent submissions without polluting the GreenDIGIT community.

- **Stage B (publishable only):** only curated, validated, and explicitly selected experiments are promoted into the GreenDIGIT Zenodo community.

This staged approach preserves traceability (all experiments remain addressable) and keeps GreenDIGIT-facing records limited to publishable outcomes.

This two-stage model also supports a clean division of responsibilities: EcoJupyter triggers packaging and submits a publication request; SoBigData services handle DOI minting, Zenodo deposition, and community assignment; and GreenDIGIT receives only the selected publishable outcomes.

In the current FDMI (D4Science) setup, this staging is realised through a dedicated Zenodo Community managed by SoBigData. This Community is titled “**GreenDIGIT FDMI Staging**”, which serves as the default target for *non-curated* object deposits prior to any promotion to the “GreenDIGIT Community”.

Minimal API handling on the EcoJupyter side

Extending the base functionality provided by SoBigData/FDMI endpoints, EcoJupyter only requires two types of behaviour in the publication request/response contract:

1. **Return the DOI in the response (DOI “lock-in”):** for the current implementation, the Zenodo DOI is retrieved manually by the user through the FDMI web user interface, once the research object has been published. In later iterations, the same DOI is expected to become retrievable programmatically; this should align with the existing item retrieval interface (e.g., via `GET /items/{ITEM_ID}` including the Zenodo DOI in the response). EcoJupyter stores this DOI as the stable handle for (1) referencing the experiment in documentation and reports; and for (2) enabling later promotion (without needing to re-upload or re-create local artefacts).
2. **A promotion flag for GreenDIGIT community submission:** in the current implementation the user may “promote” to the curated GreenDIGIT Community by manually accessing the FDMI web user interface. This promotion indicates that the submitted experiment is considered publishable and therefore eligible for inclusion in the GreenDIGIT Community in Zenodo. In later iterations the same behaviour is expected to be supported programmatically through the existing API flow, using a *boolean* flag to indicate whether the promotion should be performed.

All details regarding how Zenodo depositions are created, updated, versioned, or promoted (including community assignment mechanics) remain implementation-specific and are handled within the SoBigData/FDMI services. EcoJupyter simply (1) requests publication with a clear intent (working vs publishable) and (2) receives the DOI needed for stable referencing.

6 Further Developments

The developments and research activities related to Experimental research reproducibility will be continued, mostly within task T7.3, aimed to prototype a platform for Reproducibility as a Service, extending both stages: documenting experiments with energy consumption related information and environmental impact reproducibility conditions, and energy and environmental impact aware experiment deployment and execution based on embedded conditions and rules. EcoJupyter researcher dashboard tool will be developed to support energy aware experiment reproducibility and operation. Extending EcoJupyter for other project related tools development is planned as well. The information below provides more information on the planned development.

6.1 Extending Experiment Reproducibility with the MARTE Platform

Envisioned outcomes include a reproduction methodology for testbed-driven experiments called MARTE. MARTE aims to address the challenges of reproducing experimental results in RI-based research, which often suffer from intricate dependencies and diverse execution environments. The methodology is built upon two core approaches: malleable reproduction and automated record-replay. Malleable reproduction focuses on retaining original scripts, allowing researchers the flexibility to modify and reuse them, thereby fostering new ideas with minimal effort. This approach also proposes a new configuration file format to consolidate documentation of invocation details, execution parameters, environment settings, and dependencies. In parallel, automated record-replay ensures precise re-execution by automatically capturing all instructions issued to the experiment controller, with plans to extend the 'pos' daemon to record these instructions and their payloads in the background for one-click replay capabilities.

A significant aspect of MARTE's future development involves robust data management and sharing. The methodology further integrates RO-Crate, a standardised data packaging approach, to store experiment results alongside comprehensive metadata about their execution and environment. This integration aims to create a seamless link between experiment execution and documentation, ensuring that all configurations and dependencies are preserved and easily accessible. Future enhancements include providing an option to integrate used operating system images into the RO-Crate artifact. Furthermore, MARTE is designed to facilitate straightforward publication and sharing of experiments through standardised formats, aspiring to build an extensive, categorised collection of shareable and reproducible experiments. To enhance accessibility, there are plans to develop a user-friendly website representation of the RO-Crate artifact, bridging the gap between machine-readable JSON-LD and human-readable formats.

The project also emphasises the portability of experiments, ensuring that they can be reproduced across various testbeds and RIs. The overarching goal of MARTE is to minimise the effort required from researchers to achieve reproducibility by automating key aspects of experiment documentation, re-execution, and publication.

A planned future development for the Reproducibility as a Service platform includes the creation of a system for user-friendly visualisations of RO-Crate data. Leveraging the RO-Crate standard, this

system will enable the generation of intuitive website representations of experiment artifacts, encompassing all metadata, scripts, and results. The primary goal of this visualisation concept is to bridge the gap between machine-readable JSON-LD data and a more human-readable format, significantly simplifying how researchers interact with their work. By providing an easily navigable interface, this system will empower researchers to effortlessly browse through experiment details, understand complex configurations, and explore results. Furthermore, it will facilitate the modification of existing work by offering a clear overview of all components, and crucially, enhance the sharing process by making experiments more accessible and comprehensible to a wider audience, ultimately promoting collaboration and wider adoption of reproducible research practices.

Further developments in this project focus on enhancing data provenance and promoting more sustainable resource utilization. We plan to integrate a comprehensive accounting and billing system to track hardware resource consumption. For research institutions that both provide and use resources, a token-based system will ensure equitable sharing. Industry partners and other entities that don't contribute resources will operate under a fiscal payment model. Both of these systems will employ cryptographic algorithms to create a decentralized and transparent management structure, ensuring accountability in how resources are provisioned and used. This will also enable the secure linking of research data to RIs and individual scientists through the use of electronic signatures and seals.

6.2 EcoJupyter Validation and Extension

Building upon the initial deployment and evaluation of the EcoJupyter tool as a sustainability-focused JupyterLab extension, several improvements are planned to enhance its adoption across federated RIs and cement its role as a platform-agnostic tool for Reproducibility as a Service (RaaS).

Firstly, the focus will be given to *Platform Integration and Portability Validation* - a pivotal goal of EcoJupyter is to be a lightweight and modular component, effortlessly integrable in a Jupyter-based RI environment. Future development includes the validation of the tool's *reproducibility* requirement by reenacting experiments through deployment of the energy-aware experiment from the FDMI-exported data. Efforts also in this axis include a systematic validation of *platform agnosticism* by testing the tool across a representative set of infrastructures.

The goal is to confirm the tool's core functionality - *tracking, reporting, and publishing* sustainability metrics, remains interoperable regardless of the platform and environment. Ultimately, the tool shall be tested *Federated Testbed and Environments* to test various scenarios across heterogeneous RI configurations. These testbeds shall assess whether the *reproducibility*, exported metadata, and KPI measurements can be reliably extended to these heterogeneous environments. Focus will be given to interoperability between systems and the accuracy of the Software Carbon Intensity (SCI) KPI varying contexts.

This *Iteration and Validation of Sustainability KPIs* should extend the current prototype using *SCI, Energy per Unit, and operational emissions*. Their contextualisation and formulation across different domains and use-cases must be tested and refined to properly fit relevant scenarios—recalibrating

not only formulas with real-world energy measurements, assumptions and demands (provided by WP6), but also validating its usefulness for the end-user, the *Researcher*.

Furthermore, developments about more granular experiment tracking are envisioned. This potentially includes cell-level metric tracking within Jupyter Notebooks, allowing researchers to associate sustainability data with individual cell blocks.

These future development axes align with GreenDIGIT broader objective and scope to prototype a *reproducible, sustainable, and flexible* research platform tool. EcoJupyter serves as a user or researcher-facing tool that operationalises the 4-Pillar Conceptual Reproducibility Framework (Chapter 3.1) while embedding sustainability monitoring in real-time into the experimental lifecycle.

7 Conclusion

The presented GreenDIGIT Deliverable 5.1 introduces a web-based VRE that advances reproducible, sustainable, and Open Science-compliant RIs. Built on Jupyter notebooks, the VRE supports researchers throughout the experiment lifecycle, from design to publication, while prioritising environmental responsibility. This document outlined a comprehensive framework developed to significantly improve the reproducibility of scientific experiments throughout their entire lifecycle. We established a foundational conceptual reproducibility framework, integrating RO-Crate extensions to enable streamlined workflows and the thorough capture of essential metadata. Our solution provided a web-based VRE serving as a platform for conducting reproducible experiments. This aimed to ensure trustworthy results and eliminate the need for repeated experimental work. A core aspect involved supporting experiment design in line with Open Science principles, while also contributing to environmental sustainability by optimizing resource use. Furthermore, we detailed the necessary tooling for publishing and storing research artifacts, guaranteeing that research outcomes could be published within federated data management infrastructures and were easily accessible for both verification and subsequent reuse.

Chapter 2 established the core principles of Open Science, FAIR data, and reproducibility, which underpin the VRE's architecture. The design, outlined in Chapter 3, includes the 4-Pillar Conceptual Reproducibility Framework. It ensures that experiments are conceptually clear, systematically executed, and preserved for reuse, aligning with standards like RO-Crate and integrating with federated data management infrastructures (FDMIs) such as SoBigData. Chapter 4 detailed the architecture of the reproducible platform, which is implemented as we described in Chapter 5. Chapter 6 gave an outlook on subsequent activities.

The four pillar framework of reproducibility is prototyped with two use cases. For one, the EcoJupyter plugin and, for another, the Web platform for experimental reproducibility with pos. The VRE's extensions, including the Reproducible Experiment Design Extension for structured, portable workflows and the EcoJupyter plugin, which delivers real-time environmental impact metrics via KPIs like SCI. The SLICES MRS, integrated into the VRE, enhances metadata management with a structured, searchable schema, complementing RO-Crate's archival format for dynamic interaction and long-term preservation. Automated FDMI publishing ensures FAIR-compliant research artifacts, boosting discoverability and collaboration. The VRE's modular design supports diverse RIs, including SLICES-RI, EBRAINS, SoBigData, and EGI, with future enhancements planned for richer metadata and integration with repositories like Zenodo and EOSC. By embedding sustainability, reproducibility, and tools like SLICES MRS, the GreenDIGIT VRE minimises resource waste, enhances transparency, and lays a robust foundation for responsible scientific research.

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Appendix A. Request to FDMI from the EcoJupyter example

```
AUTH_TOKEN="your_auth_token_here"

curl --location 'https://api.d4science.org/gcat/items' \
--header 'Content-Type: application/json' \
--header "Authorization: Bearer $AUTH_TOKEN" \
--data-raw '
{
  "name": "programmatic_test_attach_curl",
  "title": "Test Experiment Attch Curl",
  "license_id": "AFL-3.0",
  "private": false,
  "notes": "testing the new xml",
  "url": null,
  "tags": [
    {
      "name": "Test"
    }
  ],
  "resources": [
    {
      "name": "Parrot image",
      "url": "https://data.d4science.net/5Apv",
      "format": "jpg"
    }
  ],
  "extras": [
    {
      "key": "Creation Date",
      "value": "2025-05-29 "
    },
    {
      "key": "Creator",
      "value": "Alfredo Oliviero"
    },
    {
      "key": "Creator Email",
      "value": "alfredo.oliviero@isti.cnr.it"
    },
    {
      "key": "Creator Name PI (Principal Investigator)",
      "value": "creatorAlfredo Oliviero_name_pi"
    },
    {
      "key": "Environment OS",
      "value": "MacOS"
    },
    {
      "key": "Environment Platform",
      "value": "D4Scence GreenDIGIT"
    }
  ],
}
```



```
{
  {
    "key": "Experiment Dependencies",
    "value": null
  },
  {
    "key": "Experiment ID",
    "value": "123"
  },
  {
    "key": "GreenDIGIT Node",
    "value": "D4Science Pisa"
  },
  {
    "key": "Programming Language",
    "value": "xml"
  },
  {
    "key": "Project ID",
    "value": "project_id"
  },
  {
    "key": "Session reading metrics",
    "value": "session_reading_metrics"
  },
  {
    "key": "system:type",
    "value": "Experiment"
  }
]
}'
```


Appendix B.FDMI submission table EcoJupyter

field_name	label	required	data_type	notes	example
gd_node	GreenDIGIT Node	TRUE	String	SoBigData Node	SBD-IT-01
project_id	Project ID	TRUE	String	Project ID	12345abcde
experiment_id	Experiment ID	TRUE	String	Experiment ID	12345abcde
creator_id	Creator	TRUE	String	ORCID Id from the creator.	0000-0001-5109-3700
creator_name	Creator Name PI (Principal Investigator)	TRUE	String	Surname, Given Name	Adnan Tahir
creator_email	Creator Email	TRUE	String	Email address	adnan.tahir@uva.nl
creation_date	Creation Date	TRUE	Time	ISO 8601 format	2024-05-26 15:30
language	Programming Language	TRUE	String	Main programming language	Python, R, CWL, ...
environment_platform	Environment Platform	TRUE	String	Platform execution environment	Container, VM, Bare-Metal,...
environment_os	Environment OS	TRUE	String	Environment operating system and specs	Ubuntu 22.04, 32GB RAM, Docker 24
dependencies	Experiment Dependencies	TRUE	String	List of dependencies for the workflow	numpy==12.4.2 pandas==2.1.0
output_metrics	Session reading metrics	TRUE	String	Output metrics containing Prometheus readings from the session. JSON format stringified.	{ kpi_sci: 3.4, energy_avg_kwh: 4.4, ... }
ro_crate_url	RO-Crate File/URL	TRUE	String	Reference (URL, identifier,	https://.../file.zip

				or path)	
ro_crate_format	RO-Crate Format	TRUE	String	File format ("zip", "json")	ZIP
ro_crate_name	RO-Crate Name	FALSE	String	(Optional) Display name	Session123_R OCrate
ro_crate_desc	RO-Crate Description	FALSE	String	(Optional) Description	RO-Crate metadata for session workflow

Appendix C. EcoJupyter Installation, Usage and Output

The EcoJupyter plugin was designed to minimise configuration overhead while enabling rich interaction with experiment metrics and reproducibility tooling. Below is a summary of how to install, use, and interpret the results of the tool, as well as future usability improvements currently under consideration.

C.1. Installation

Installing EcoJupyter is straightforward and can be done directly from within a JupyterLab terminal:

```
pip install --upgrade ecojupyter
```

Once installed, simply reload the JupyterLab interface. The dashboard panel will now be available in the left-hand menu.

Note: When the tool is first installed, no KPIs or metrics are visible. These are only populated once an experiment has been initiated and the metrics agent is running.

C.2. Usage Instructions

1. Install Metrics Agent

Before running a workflow, the metrics collection agent (e.g., Scaphandre) must be installed and started. This is triggered through the EcoJupyter interface and is crucial for energy and system metrics to be recorded.

- **Feedback:** The installation typically takes between 2–3 minutes to complete.

2. Run Workflow

Once the metrics agent is installed:

- Begin your experiment by running the first cell of your Jupyter Notebook. This signals the start of the workflow.
- Execute your experiment as usual. EcoJupyter automatically tracks timestamps and collects data throughout the workflow.
- After the first cell is executed, click the **Refresh** button in the dashboard to begin visualising real-time KPIs.

The tool relies on the structured execution model, where the **first and last cell** mark the bounds of the experiment.

3. Automatic Publication to FDMI

Once the final cell is executed, EcoJupyter automatically triggers the packaging and publication process:

- **RO-Crate Skeleton Folder** is generated containing:

- Metadata (e.g. OS, programming language)
- Logs and environment configuration
- Input and output artefacts from the notebook
- `ro-crate-metadata.json` describes all experiment components in a FAIR-compliant format.
- **FDMI Submission:** A structured JSON is sent to the SoBigData catalogue via the API endpoint, registering the experiment, associated metrics, and metadata.

Appendix D.RO-Crate automatic generation

```
{
"@context": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/1.1/context",
"@graph": [
  {
"@id": "./",
"@type": "Dataset",
"name": "RO-Crate for test / experiment-6fb829d9-2025-07-09 14:16",
"hasPart": [
  "workflow/",
  "data/",
  "logs/",
  "environment/",
  "experiment_setup/",
  "lifecycle-analysis/",
  "README.md"
],
"license": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/"
},
  {
"@id": "ro-crate-metadata.json",
"@type": "CreativeWork",
"about": {
"@id": "."
}
},
  {
"@id": "workflow/test.ipynb",
"@type": "ComputationalWorkflow",
"name": "Jupyter Notebook workflow",
"programmingLanguage": {
"@id": "https://w3id.org/ro/crate/terms/Python"
}
}
]
}
```